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**Calculating non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions at the
farm level:**

Methods, emission factors, and data requirements with
application examples from Austria

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Calculating non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions at the farm level:

Methods, emission factors, and data requirements with application examples from Austria

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Abbreviations

AAP	Average annual population
ADF	Acid detergent fibre
AFOLU Sector	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use Sector
BAB	Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen
C	Carbon
CA	Crude ash
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CP	Crude protein
DE	Digestible energy
DFEMS	Digital non-CO ₂ farm emission monitoring system
DM	Dry matter
DMI	Dry matter intake
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EF	Emission factor
FM	Fresh matter
g	Gram
GE	Gross energy
GHG	Greenhouse gas
h	Hour
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
IACS-GIS	Integrated Administration and Control System – Geo Information System
K	potassium
kg	Kilogram
KTBL	Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft
LfL	Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft
LK	Landwirtschaftskasse
MCF	Methane conversion factor for CH ₄ emissions from manure management
ME	Metabolizable energy
MJ	Mega joule
N	Nitrogen
N ₂	Nitrogen gas
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NDF	Neutral detergent fibre
NE	Net energy
NH ₃	Ammonia
NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate
non-CO ₂ GHG	Non-carbon dioxide greenhouse gas
NO _x	Nitric oxides
P	Phosphorus
T	Livestock sub-category
VS	Volatile solids
Y _m	Methane conversion factor for CH ₄ emissions from enteric fermentation

List of variables

Variable	Unit	Description	Source
AAP(T)	number of heads	average annual population of the livestock sub-category T	farm-level data
AG _{DM} (C)	kg DM ha ⁻¹	above-ground residue DM for a certain crop	IPCC (2019)
AGR(C)	kg DM year ⁻¹	total amount of above-ground residues for a certain crop	farm-level calculation
AnnualMilkProduction (T)	kg animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	average annual milk production in one year per animal	farm-level data
area(C)	ha year ⁻¹	total area harvested of a certain crop	farm-level data
B ₀ (T)	m ³ CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ VS	maximum CH ₄ producing capacity for manure produced by livestock sub-category T	IPCC, 2019
BGR(C)	kg DM year ⁻¹	total amount of below-ground residues for a certain crop	farm-level calculation
BP	dimensionless (index)	breeding phase	farm-level data
BW _{final} (T)	kg	live weight of fattening pigs at the end of a certain growth stage	farm-level data
BW _{initial} (T)	kg	live weight of fattening pigs at the beginning of a certain growth stage	farm-level data
C	dimensionless (index)	crop type	farm-level data
CA	g kg ⁻¹	crude ash content of DMI	farm-level data
CalvingInterval(T)	days	period between the birth from one to the birth of the next calf	farm-level data
C _a	dimensionless; fraction	activity coefficient	IPCC (2019)
C _{growth} (T)	dimensionless	growth coefficient for cattle	IPCC (2019)
C _p	%, fraction	gestation coefficient	
C _i	MJ kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	maintenance coefficient for cattle	IPCC (2019)
C _{i,BP}	MJ kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	maintenance coefficient for breeding sows	van der Peet-Schwering and Bikker (2019)
C _f	MJ kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	maintenance coefficient for poultry	Jeroch et al. (2020)
C _f CH ₄ _{Total,EntFerm}	dimensionless kg CH ₄ year ⁻¹	combustion factor total CH ₄ emissions from enteric fermentation	farm-level calculation

CP	%	crude protein content of DMI	farm-level data
days _{BP} (T)	days	length of a breeding phase (breeding sows)	farm-level data
DE	%	digestible energy in a feed ration	farm-level data
DMI(T)	kg animal ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	dry matter intake	farm-level data
EF _{CH₄, EntFerm} (T)	kg CH ₄ animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	CH ₄ emission factor from enteric fermentation for livestock sub-category T	farm-level calculation
EF _{CH₄, MM} (T)	kg CH ₄ animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	CH ₄ emission factor from manure management for livestock sub-category T	farm-level calculation
EF _{(housing(NH₃))} (T)		emission factor for NH ₃ emissions from livestock housing	EEA (2019)
EF _{N₂O,MM} (S,T)	kg N ₂ O-N kg N ⁻¹ excreted	emission factor for direct N ₂ O emissions	Arbeitsgruppe BEK (2021), IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O,Ninputs}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N input) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from urine and dung N deposited on pasture range, and paddock	IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O,PRP}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N input) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from urine and dung N deposited on pasture range, and paddock	IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O, ATD}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg NH ₃ -N + NO _x -N volatilized) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N on soils and water surfaces	IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O(MM), ATD}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg NH ₃ -N + NO _x -N volatilized) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from manure management	IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O,L}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N leached and runoff) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from leaching and runoff	IPCC (2019)
EF _{N₂O(MM),L}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N leached and runoff) ⁻¹	emission factor for N ₂ O emissions from leaching and runoff from manure management	IPCC (2019)
EggProd(T)	g animal ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	egg mass production	farm-level data
EF _{housing(NH₃)} (T)	kg NH ₃ -N (kg N excreted) ⁻¹	NH ₃ emission factors for livestock housing	(Anderl et al., 2023a)
F _{AM}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of livestock manure N applied to soils	farm-level data, calculation

F_{COMP}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of total compost N applied to soils	farm-level data
F_{CR}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of N in crop residues returned to soils	farm-level data, calculation
F_{OAA}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of other organic amendments used as fertilizer, such as brewery waste	farm-level data
F_{ON}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of animal manure, compost, sewage sludge, or other organic N additions applied to soils	farm-level data
F_{PRP}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of urine and dung N deposited by grazing livestock on pasture, range and paddock	farm-level data calculation
F_{SEW}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of total sewage N that is applied to soils	farm-level data
F_{SN}	kg N year ⁻¹	amount of synthetic N fertilizer applied to soils	farm-level data
$FM_{Digestate}(T)$	kg year ⁻¹	amount of fresh matter digestate of livestock category T	farm-level data
$FR(T)$	parturitions year ⁻¹	fertility rate of breeding sows	farm-level data
$FRAC_{burnt}(C)$	%	fraction of annual harvested area of a certain crop that is burnt	farm-level data
$FRAC_{constr}$	%	fraction of managed manure used for construction	farm-level data
$FRAC_{DM}(C)$	%	DM fraction of the harvested crop C in kg DM per kg fresh weight	LfL (2023, 2021a, 2021b), LK Oberösterreich (2020)
$FRAC_{feed}$	%	fraction of managed manure used for feed	farm-level data
$FRAC_{fuel}$	%	fraction of managed manure burned for fuel	farm-level data
$FRAC_{gasMM}(S,T)$	%	fraction of managed manure N that volatilizes as NH ₃ and NO _x	IPCC (2019)
$FRAC_{gasSoilM}$	kg N (kg applied N) ⁻¹	fraction of applied organic N (FON) and of urine and dung N deposited by grazing animals (FPRP) that	IPCC (2019), Anderl et al. (2023b), EEA (2019)

$FRAC_{gasSoilSN}$	kg N (kg applied N) ⁻¹	volatilizes as NH ₃ and NO _x fraction of synthetic fertilizer N that volatilizes as NH ₃ and NO _x	IPCC (2019), Anderl et al. (2023b), EEA (2019)
$FRAC_{leachSoil}$	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N leached and runoff) ⁻¹	fraction of all N sources added to or mineralized in managed agricultural soils that is lost through leaching and runoff	IPCC (2019)
$FRAC_{leachMM}(S,T)$		fraction of managed manure N that is leached	IPCC (2019)
$FRAC_{lossMM}(S,T)$	%	total fraction of managed manure N lost in a manure management system	farm-level calculation
$FRAC_{N_2MM}(S,T)$	%	fraction of managed manure N lost as N ₂	farm-level calculation
$FRAC_{remove}(C)$	%	fraction of AGR of a certain crop removed annually for purposes such as bedding	farm-level data
$FRAC_{renew}(C)$	%	fraction of the total area under a certain crop that is renewed annually	farm-level data
$GE(T)$	MJ day ⁻¹ animal ⁻¹	gross energy of the feed ration	farm-level data; farm-level calculation
$GestRate(T)$	dimensionless	gestation rate per year of a typical animal in livestock sub-category T	farm-level data
$GestLength(T)$	dimensionless	length of the gestation period for breeding sows	farm-level data
$LitterSize(T)$	heads	average litter size per parturition	farm-level data
$LactationPeriod(T)$	days	lactation period in days	farm-level data
$livestock_{count}(T)$	heads	number of heads in the livestock sub-category T	farm-level data
$LW_{mature}(T)$	kg	mature live weight of animals	farm-level data
$MCF(S,T)$	%	CH ₄ conversion factor for CH ₄ emissions from manure management depending on S	Amon et al. (2007, 2006); Anderl et al. (2023b), Haenel et al. (2020), IPCC (2006)
$ME_g(T)$	MJ animal ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	metabolizable energy for maintenance	farm-level calculation

$ME_m(T)$	$MJ\ animal^{-1}\ day^{-1}$	metabolizable energy for maintenance	farm-level calculation
$ME_p(T)$	$MJ\ animal^{-1}\ day^{-1}$	metabolizable energy for performance	farm-level calculation
MilkFat(T)	%	fat content of the milk	farm-level data
MilkProtein(T)	%	protein content of the milk	farm-level data
MilkProduction(T)	$kg\ animal^{-1}\ day^{-1}$	daily milk production of the livestock sub-category T	farm-level data
MS(S,T)	%	fraction of manure of a specific livestock sub-category T that is handled in a specific manure storage system S	farm-level data
$MS_{PRP}(T)$	%	fraction of the excreted N deposited on pasture, range and paddock	farm-level data
$N_2O_D(MM)$	$kg\ year^{-1}$	direct N_2O emissions from manure management	farm-level calculation
$N_2O_D(Soils)$	$kg\ year^{-1}$	direct N_2O emissions from managed agricultural soils	farm-level calculation
N_2O-N_{inputs}	$kg\ N_2O-N\ year^{-1}$	annual direct N_2O-N emissions from N inputs to soils	farm-level calculation
N_2O-N_{PRP}	$kg\ N_2O-N\ year^{-1}$	annual direct N_2O-N emissions from N deposited by grazing livestock to soils	farm-level calculation
$N_2O_G(Soils)$	$kg\ N_2O\ year^{-1}$	annual N_2O-N emissions from atmospheric deposition of N that is volatilized from managed soils	farm-level calculation
$N_2O_G(MM)$	$kg\ N_2O\ year^{-1}$	indirect N_2O emissions from manure management due to volatilization	farm-level calculation
$N_2O_L(MM)$	$kg\ N_2O\ year^{-1}$	indirect N_2O emissions from manure management due to leaching	farm-level calculation
$N_2O_L(Soils)$	$kg\ N_2O\ year^{-1}$	indirect N_2O emissions from managed agricultural soils due to leaching	farm-level calculation
$N_{AG}(C)$	$kg\ N\ (kg\ DM)^{-1}$	N content of AGR(C) for a certain crop	IPCC (2019)
$N_{bedding}(S,T)$	$kg\ animal^{-1}\ year^{-1}$	amount of N from bedding	farm-level data

$N_{BG}(C)$	$kg (kg DM)^{-1}$	N content of below-ground residues for a certain crop	IPCC (2019)
$N_{biogas}(S, T)$	$kg year^{-1}$	amount of N added from the anaerobic digestion system	farm-level calculation
$N_{ContentBiogas}(T)$	$kg N (1,000 kg FM digestate)^{-1}$	kg N per 1,000 kg of fresh matter digestate of livestock category T	(Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021)
N_{egg}	$kg kg^{-1}$	average N content in eggs	IPCC (2019)
$N_{gain}(T)$	$kg animal^{-1} year^{-1}$	amount of N retained in the livestock sub-categories through growth	farm-level calculation; (IPCC (2019), based on Poulsen & Kristensen 1998; FAO, 2017)
$N_{intake}(T)$	$kg animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	daily N intake from feed	farm-level calculation
$N_{leaching}(MM)$	$kg N year^{-1}$	N lost through leaching	farm-level calculation
$N_{MMavl}(S, T)$	$kg year^{-1}$	amount of manure N available for application to soil	farm-level calculation
$N_{retention}(T)$	$kg animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	daily amount of N retained by the animal	farm-level calculation
$N_{volatilisation}(MM)$	$kg year^{-1}$	NH_3 emissions (i.e., N losses) due to volatilization	farm-level calculation
$N_{weanedPiglets}(T)$	$kg animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	amount of N retained in piglets weaned	farm-level calculation
$NE_a(T)$	$MJ animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	net energy for activity	farm-level calculation
$NE_g(T)$	$MJ animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	net energy for growth	farm-level calculation
$NE_l(T)$	$MJ animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	net energy for lactation	farm-level calculation
$NE_m(T)$	$MJ animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	net energy for maintenance	farm-level calculation
$NE_p(T)$	$MJ animal^{-1} day^{-1}$	net energy for gestation	farm-level calculation
$N_{ex}(T)$	$kg animal^{-1} year^{-1}$	annual N excretion rate	farm-level calculation
$N_{ex}(S)$	kg manure in manure management system S $year^{-1}$	N excretion per manure management system	farm-level calculation
$NH_{3(housing)}$		NH_3 emissions from livestock housing	farm-level calculation
$NH_{3(storage)}$		NH_3 emissions from livestock manure storage	farm-level calculation
NumberAnnualGestations(T)	number animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	number of gestations per sow per year	farm-level data
pigletWtbirth	kg	birth weight of piglets	farm-level data

pigletWtweaned	kg	live weight of piglets at weaning age	farm-level data
OM _{immobil}	dimensionless	fraction of the TAN that is immobilised	EEA (2019)
ProductionPeriod(T)	days	time period from birth to slaughter or within one livestock sub-category	farm-level data
R _{N2(N2O)}	kg N ₂ -N (kg N ₂ O-N) ⁻¹	ratio of N ₂ :N ₂ O emissions	IPCC (2019)
Ratio(C)	kg DM per ha (kg DM per ha) ⁻¹	ratio of below-ground root biomass to above-ground shoot biomass	IPCC (2019)
Ratio _{YieldAG} (C)	dimensionless	ratio of above-ground residue DM to the harvested yield for a certain crop	IPCC (2019)
REG	dimensionless	ratio of net energy available for growth to digestible anergy	farm-level calculation
REM	dimensionless	ratio of net energy available for maintenance to digestible energy	farm-level calculation
S	dimensionless (index)	manure storage system	farm-level data
Straw _{FM} (T)	kg fresh weight animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	amount of bedding	farm-level data
T	dimensionless (index)	livestock sub-category	farm-level data
TAN _{content} (T)	fkg NH ₄ -N (Nex(T) ⁻¹)	TAN content of the livestock manure	EEA (2019)
TotalMilkProdLactation(T)	kg animal ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	average total annual milk production in one lactation period	farm-level data
UE	dimensionless	urinary energy expressed as a fraction of GE	IPCC (2019)
VS(T)	kg DM animal ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	daily volatile solids expected per livestock sub-category T	farm-level calculation
Weight(T)	kg	live weight of animals	farm-level data
WG(T)	g or kg day ⁻¹	average daily weight gain of growing livestock	farm-level data
WG _{fat} (T)	g kg ⁻¹	ratio of fat gain to weight gain in g per kg	farm-level calculation
WG _{protein} (T)	g kg ⁻¹	ratio of protein gain to weight gain in g per kg	farm-level calculation
WG ^{LS} _{fat} (T)	g day ⁻¹	fat deposition of suckling pigs	farm-level calculation
WG ^{LS} _{protein} (T)	g day ⁻¹	protein deposition of suckling pigs	farm-level calculation
Y _m (T)	%	CH ₄ conversion factor as a percentage of GE	IPCC (2019, tab. 10.12), Anderl et al., 2023b, tab. 8

YieldDM(C)	kg DM ha ⁻¹	in the feed converted to CH ₄ harvested dry matter yield for a certain crop	farm-level data, calculation
YieldFM(C)	kg FM ha ⁻¹	harvested fresh-mass yield for a certain crop	farm-level data

1. Motivation and scope

Globally, the agricultural sector is the main emitter of non-carbon dioxide greenhouse gases (non-CO₂ GHG), namely methane (CH₄) from enteric fermentation, CH₄, nitrous oxide (N₂O) from manure management, and N₂O from managed agricultural soils. In Austria, the agricultural sector accounted for 9.3% of the total national GHG emissions in 2021 (Anderl et al., 2023b). Thereof, non-CO₂ GHG emissions from enteric fermentation and agricultural soils took the largest shares, with 5.4% and 2.3% of the total national GHG emissions, respectively (Anderl et al., 2023b).

GHG emissions must be reduced in all sectors – including agriculture – to meet the EU and Austrian climate neutrality targets until 2050 and 2040, respectively (BKA Österreich, 2020; European Commission, 2018). Technical (e.g., feed supplements, nitrogen inhibitors), structural (e.g., shift to high-intensity management systems), and management changes (e.g., feeding strategy, manure handling), have been found to be highly efficient mitigation measures for reducing non-CO₂ GHG emissions in the agricultural sector (Frank et al., 2018). However, emission fluxes and mitigation potentials at farm level are subject to uncertainties, mostly because of inaccuracies and uncertainties in input data and an imperfect characterization of emission factors (Anderl et al., 2023a; Leip et al., 2018, 2011). Emission factors are defined as “*coefficients that quantify the emissions or removal of gas per unit of activity*” (IPCC, 2019, p. G.7), i.e., representative values that relate the amount of emissions to a specific farming activity.

We suggest that farm-level emission monitoring may reduce such uncertainties and facilitate the implementation of effective and efficient mitigation measures on farms. Hence, we aim to develop a prototype of a digital non-CO₂ farm emission monitoring system (DFEMS) by building on established GHG emission calculation approaches and emission factors, e.g., the guidelines provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2019, 2006), and by collecting data on farming activities to replace default values with farm-level data for more accurate estimates of emissions at the farm level.

Here, we present a structured overview, hereafter referred to as protocol, on methods and farm-level data required to implement such a DFEMS (see Appendix 1). The protocol is based on a review of calculation approach, available emission factors, and literature relevant for farm-level emission monitoring systems. Additionally, state-of-the-art datasets such as administrative data, data from the Integrated Administration and Control System IACS and IACS-GIS, and farm survey data were reviewed in order to identify farm-level data that is additionally needed for calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level. We present an overview on (i) the IPCC guidelines for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting, (ii) calculation approaches and emission factors for CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from manure management, N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils, as well ammonia (NH₃) emissions from manure management, livestock housing and soils; and (iii) data requirements for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting at the farm level. In addition, we give examples of how we have implemented the suggested approach for the Austrian agriculture. The protocol focuses on the farming activities within the farm gate: It neither includes GHG emissions resulting from the production of farm inputs, such as feed imports and the production of mineral fertilizer and machinery, nor from subsequent steps in the value chain, such as, further processing of primary products. It addresses the livestock categories cattle, swine, and poultry, which are responsible for the largest share of the non-CO₂ GHG emissions in the agricultural sector in Austria. The average non-CO₂ GHG emissions are calculated for one year, while interannual dynamics and changes at the farm are only considered for feed rations (summer and winter feed rations) and feeding situations (e.g., grazing period in summer and livestock confined in a stall during winter); changes in livestock numbers are not accounted for. Therefore, the approach presented in this protocol provides a snapshot of the non-CO₂ GHG emissions for an individual farm in one year.

2. Overview of methods for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting at the farm level

The IPCC has developed three levels of methods for estimating non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agriculture: tier 1, tier 2, and tier 3 (IPCC, 2006, 2019) with increasing complexity and data needs. The choice of approach is based on the purpose of the emission accounting, the available data and

resources. The tier 2 and tier 3 are adequate approaches for accurately estimating farm-level non-CO₂ GHG emissions, considering site-specific production conditions and farm management practices.

The tier 1 approach is characterized by default emission factors and simple equations for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting from agriculture. It is a straightforward and widely used approach, but it does neither account for site-specific production conditions, nor for farm management practices. The tier 1 approach for calculating CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation is based on livestock characteristics (e.g., differentiating between livestock sub-categories such as dairy cows and other cattle), the average annual number of animals per livestock (sub-) category, and on default CH₄ emission factors. An enhanced tier 1 approach for calculating CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation provides default emission factors differentiating between low and high productivity systems for cattle. A low productivity system is defined as a traditional production system where cattle is kept for multiple purposes, providing draft power, i.e., animal power, as well as, e.g., milk production. A high productivity system occurs when the livestock sector is commercialised; this system is market oriented (IPCC, 2019). The tier 1 approach for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting from manure management and agricultural soils applies average values, e.g., for the nitrogen (N) excreted per animal of a certain livestock category, and default emission factors for the N losses.

The tier 2 approach differentiates between livestock sub-categories (differentiation e.g., by age, production intensity and sex) and accounts for farm management practices by using disaggregated emission factors and parameters in the IPCC equations. The tier 2 approach for calculating the CH₄ emission factor and, subsequently, the CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, is based on feed intake estimates for a typical animal in each defined livestock sub-category. The tier 2 approach for calculating CH₄ emissions from manure management relies on volatile solids excreted by each livestock sub-category, on the maximum methane producing capacity of a certain livestock manure, and on the methane conversion factor for each manure storage system. The direct and indirect N₂O emissions from manure depend on the N excreted and on the type of manure storage system. The tier 2 approach for calculating N₂O from managed soils is based on more detailed farm activity data, as well as country-specific emission factors; the same equations as in tier 1 are applied.

The tier 3 approach uses process-based simulation models for estimating non-CO₂ GHG emissions. These models require extensive input data on farm management practices, animal feeding, and soil and climate conditions, making it the most resource-intensive approach. However, it may provide more accurate results.

In the protocol we present the equations provided by the IPCC and demonstrate how to apply them to farm-level and country-specific data, making it a tier 2 approach (IPCC, 2006, 2019). Country-specific data is needed that addresses emission factors and parameters for calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions, as provided by Austria's National Inventory Report (see Anderl et al., 2023b for the latest version). Data provided by the European Environmental Agency (EEA; European Environment Agency, 2019) are included for further disaggregating emission factors (e.g., emission factors for NH₃ losses differentiated between fertilizer types). The database on disaggregated emission factors provided by the Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft (KTBL; see Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021) serves as another data source. This German initiative collects standard methods for calculating farm-level GHG emissions, emission factors and parameters to increase transparency and comparability with other (research) projects. The KTBL provides, for instance, emission factors that consider the type of manure by housing systems and livestock categories, the cover of manure storage systems, the manure application methods, and the manure incorporation time. These disaggregated emission factors capture different farm management practices and their respective rate of releasing non-CO₂ GHG emissions to the atmosphere.

Box 1: Data collection for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

For the application examples of a DFEMS from Austria, the data requirements according to the IPCC equations and the above-mentioned additions through more differentiated emission factors were compared with the available farm-level data in Austria. This comparison formed the basis to identify data gaps that need to be closed for the DFEMS. For filling the identified data gaps, an existing web-based farm management system (hereafter also referred to as data query tool) was used and extended with additional data queries on livestock characteristics, feeding strategies and composition, crop production and soil management, as well as on manure storage systems.

3. Non-CO₂ GHG emissions from livestock and manure management

3.1. Livestock related farm-level input data

3.1.1. Livestock categories and population

For all livestock farms, detailed information on livestock characteristics, livestock management (e.g., feeding strategy), and manure management provides the basis for calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management.

The first step is the identification and definition of livestock categories and respective sub-categories. The livestock sub-categories should be homogeneous and can be based on characteristics such as type or purpose of production (e.g., fattening or breeding purposes), age and sex. The defined livestock categories and sub-categories should be used consistently throughout the whole chain of non-CO₂ GHG emission sources, i.e., non-CO₂ GHG emissions from enteric fermentation, from manure management and managed agricultural soils. This means that for each defined livestock sub-category at a farm, CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation are calculated separately, N excretion rates are derived for a representative animal per livestock sub-category, and similarly, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from manure management are calculated for each defined livestock sub-category.

The defined livestock sub-categories can be even further divided based on variations in feeding and/or housing practices within a livestock sub-category. For instance, dry cows can form a sub-category due to a different feeding strategy for a certain period of the year. Similarly, fattening pigs can be divided into sub-categories based on different feeding phases until slaughter. A further sub-categorization is only recommended and useful if farm-level data is available and accessible for calculating the non-CO₂ GHG emissions across the different emission sources, i.e., from enteric fermentation and manure management.

Box 2: Livestock sub-categories for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the application examples of the DFEMS, we focus on cattle, swine, and poultry farms due to their relevance in the Austrian agricultural sector and their resulting importance for and share in total non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agriculture. We further subdivide these livestock categories into the following livestock sub-categories:

- Cattle
 - Dairy cattle
 - Suckling cows
 - Young cattle up to 1 year
 - Slaughter calves up to 6 months
 - Calves up to 6 months
 - Young cattle 6 months up to 1 year
 - Young cattle 1-2 years
 - Breeding cattle: heifers 1-2 years
 - Fattening cattle: oxen and bulls 1-2 years, fattening heifers 1-2 years
 - Other cattle > 2 years (e.g., breeding bulls, stud bulls)
- Swine
 - Piglets up to 8 kg live weight, i.e., litter – not considered as a swine sub-category for non-CO₂ emission calculation, but included in the energy requirement calculation of breeding sows
 - Piglets 8-32 kg live weight
 - Fattening pigs, i.e., swine from 32 kg until the end of the fattening period/ mating
 - Breeding sows
 - Breeding boars
- Poultry
 - Chicks and pullets for laying purposes
 - Laying hens and roosters
 - Broiler chickens

After defining the livestock sub-categories, the second step involves an accurate estimation of the livestock herd size. The size of the livestock herd, i.e., number of animals per livestock sub-category, is a key farm-specific information for calculating farm-level non-CO₂ GHG emissions by, e.g., multiplying it by the calculated livestock sub-category-specific CH₄ emission factor or the N excretion rates. Livestock-related non-CO₂ GHG emissions are calculated per animal on an annual basis, i.e., the DFEMS is applied at an annual basis. For mature livestock, such as dairy cows, suckling cows, breeding sows, or breeding boars, the **average annual population (AAP)** is obtained at a reference date and assumed to be constant throughout the year. For growing animals with a lifespan less than one year (e.g., fattening pigs, broilers) and for animals that are part of more than one livestock sub-category during their life (e.g., calves which become heifers and subsequently dairy cows), it is assumed that the number of animal places occupied is constant throughout the year. Therefore, the AAP for livestock sub-categories T with a lifespan less than one year is given by

$$AAP(T) = \begin{cases} \text{ProductionPeriod}(T) * \left(\frac{\text{livestock}_{\text{count}}(T)}{365} \right), \\ \text{livestock}_{\text{count}}(T); \end{cases} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows, other cattle } > 2 \text{ years,} \\ \text{breeding sows, breeding boars}\} \quad (1)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.1), where $\text{ProductionPeriod}(T)$ is the time period from birth to slaughter or the time within a certain livestock sub-category T in days, and $\text{livestock}_{\text{count}}(T)$ is the total number of animals produced annually of each livestock sub-category T. This approach is applied to avoid overestimating the non-CO₂ GHG emission due to double counting, as well as to account for differences in production intensities, i.e., different fattening periods. Moreover, it allows to use the unit “per animal” (animal⁻¹) for all livestock sub-categories when calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions. For plausibility checks, data on the number of growing cycles per year can be used alternatively to calculate the AAP for the livestock sub-category T.

3.1.2. Livestock characteristics and parameters

The calculation of the performance-specific feed intake for a livestock sub-category builds the basis for calculating CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation as well as from manure management at the farm level. As the livestock performance not only varies between different livestock sub-categories, but also by farm, the following data on livestock characteristics is **needed for all livestock sub-categories** distinguishing between mature and growing livestock:

- **Average live weight (kg animal⁻¹):** We assume a constant live weight for livestock that has not the primary purpose of body mass growth. Therefore, for mature livestock, i.e., the sub-categories dairy cows, suckling cows, other cattle over 2 years (e.g., breeding bulls, stud bulls), breeding sows and breeding boars, the average live weight of a typical animal in the sub-category is needed. The live weight of livestock influences the energy requirements, i.e., the amount of feed consumed by the animal.

However, for all **growing livestock sub-categories**, such as young cattle, breeding and fattening cattle, fattening pigs and broiler chicks, the weight at several production phases is needed:

- The **start weight (in kg)** is the average weight with which an animal enters a defined livestock sub-category. The start weight is equivalent to the **weight at birth or hatching** for the livestock sub-categories belonging to young cattle up to 1 year, piglets, pullets or broiler chicken.
- The **end weight (in kg)** refers to the live weight of an animal at the end of the production phase in a certain livestock sub-category. The end weight is equivalent to the **slaughter live weight** for animals that only belong to one livestock sub-category without considering further production phases, e.g., broiler chicken.
- **Average weight gain per day (g animal⁻¹ day⁻¹):** The average weight gain per day indicates the level of production intensity and determines the feed ration. Mature livestock (e.g., dairy cows, suckling cows) is assumed to have a net weight gain of 0 g animal⁻¹ day⁻¹. Weight gains due to e.g., gestation, are not considered in non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting.

In addition, growth curves can support estimating the live weight of animals. The carcass weight (kg) can be used for cross checking, whereby the relationship between live and carcass weight can vary depending on body conditions and breed.

Box 3: Information on live weight of livestock sub-categories at different growing phases for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

If detailed farm-level data on average live weight and weight gain is not available, the standard gross margin catalogue (Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen (BAB), 2022) provides comprehensive information on weight at birth, at weaning and at slaughtering as well as information on average daily weight gain for livestock in Austria. In the DFEMS, we further use this information for plausibility checks of queried farm-level data.

Table 1: Start weight, end weight and average daily weight gain for different growing livestock sub-categories (adapted from BAB, 2022)

Livestock sub-category	Breed / Intensity	Start weight (kg)	Weight gain (g day ⁻¹)	End weight (kg)	Rearing days (days)
Young cattle up to 1 year*	Fleckvieh	80	750	307	302
	Braunvieh	65	750	302	316
	Pinzgauer	65	700	286	316
	Grauvieh	65	700	286	316
	Holstein Friesian	65	750	302	316
Young cattle 1-2 years; Breeding cattle: Heifers	Fleckvieh	307	664	549	365
	Braunvieh	302	618	528	365
	Pinzgauer	286	530	480	365
	Grauvieh	286	444	448	365
	Holstein Friesian	302	714	563	365
(Breeding) Cattle >2 Years	Fleckvieh	549	618	570	34
	Braunvieh	528	530	570	80
	Pinzgauer	480	444	545	147
	Grauvieh	448	714	490	59
	Holstein Friesian	563	618	570	12
Young cattle: Fattening cattle (female) up to 1 year	extensive	90	800	332	303
	extensive + organic	90	750	317	303
	extensive, own production	75	800	303	285
	extensive, own production + organic	75	750	289	285
	intensive	90	900	363	303
	intensive + organic	90	850	348	303
	intensive, own production	75	900	332	285
	intensive, own production + organic	75	850	317	285
Young cattle: Fattening cattle (female) 1-2 years	extensive	332	800	586	317
	extensive + organic	317	750	586	358
	extensive, own production	303	800	585	353
	extensive, own production + organic	289	750	563	365
	intensive	363	900	586	248

	intensive + organic	348	850	586	280
	intensive + organic	332	900	586	282.3
	intensive, own production	317	850	586	316
Young cattle: Fattening cattle (male) up to 1 year*	bulls	110	1320	554	336
	bulls, Fleckvieh	90	1320	491	304
	bulls, Braunvieh	65	1090	365	275
	bulls, Pinzgauer	75	1140	400	285
	bulls, Grauvieh	70	1100	378	280
	bulls, Holstein Friesian	65	1010	343	275
	oxes, milkbreed, extensive + organic	110	850	396	336
	oxes, milkbreed, intensive + organic	110	800	379	336
	oxes, milkbreed from own production, extensive + organic	70	850	308	280
	oxes, milkbreed from own production, intensive + organic	71	800	295	280
	oxes, multi-purpose breed, extensive + organic	110	850	396	336
	oxes, multi-purpose breed, intensive + organic	110	800	379	336
	oxes, multi-purpose breed from own production, extensive + organic	80	850	327	291
	oxes, multi-purpose breed from own production, intensive + organic	80	800	313	291
Fattening cattle (male, oxes and bulls) 1-2 years	bulls	554	1320	729	133
	bulls, Fleckvieh	491	1320	729	180
	bulls, Braunvieh	365	1090	631	244
	bulls, Pinzgauer	400	1140	583	161
	bulls, Grauvieh	378	1100	670	265
	bulls, Holstein Friesian	343	1010	683	337
	oxes, milkbreed, extensive + organic	396	850	617	260
	oxes, milkbreed, intensive + organic	379	800	649	338
	oxes, milkbreed from own production, extensive + organic	308	850	617	363
	oxes, milkbreed from own production, intensive + organic	295	800	587	365
	oxes, multi-purpose breed, extensive + organic	396	850	700	358
	oxes, multi-purpose breed, intensive + organic	379	800	644	332
	oxes, multi-purpose breed from own production, extensive + organic	327	850	638	365
	oxes, multi-purpose breed from own production, intensive + organic	313	800	605	365
Fattening pigs	low production intensity	31	749	120	119
	medium production intensity	31	786	120	113
	high production intensity	31	823	120	108
	low production intensity + organic	31	650	131	154
	medium production intensity + organic	31	710	131	141

high production intensity + organic 31 770 131 130

* Own calculation: e.g., assumption for the age at weaning = 9 weeks → 302 rearing days in the first year; start weight + (daily weight gain in g * rearing days during first year) / 1,000 = start weight in the second year

Specific activity and performance data requirements for cattle farms

In addition to the data required for all livestock sub-categories, specific activity and performance data are required from cattle farms:

- For lactating cattle, i.e., dairy cows and suckling cows, a key performance criterion is the **average daily milk production** (MilkProduction(T), in kg animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) per livestock sub-category T. The average daily milk production can be calculated based on a year, i.e., 365 days (see eq. (2)), or the lactation period (see eq. (3)). MilkProduction(T) is given by

$$\text{MilkProduction}(T) = \frac{\text{AnnualMilkProduction}(T)}{365} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (2)$$

(own calculation), where AnnualMilkProduction(T) is the average annual milk production in kg per animal and year; or

$$\text{MilkProduction}(T) = \frac{\text{TotalMilkProdLactation}(T)}{\text{LactationPeriod}(T)} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (3)$$

(own calculation), where TotalMilkProdLactation(T) is the annual milk production in kg per animal in one lactation period and LactationPeriod(T) is the lactation period in days.

- The average **milk fat and milk protein content (%)** are needed for lactating cattle, i.e., dairy and suckling cows.
- The rate of **gestation per year** (GestRate(T), dimensionless) is needed for lactating cattle, i.e., dairy cows and suckling cows. The gestation rate is expressed as

$$\text{GestRate}(T) = \frac{365}{\text{CalvingInterval}(T)} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (4)$$

(Hörtenhuber et al., 2023), where CalvingInterval(T) is the period between the birth from one to the birth of the next calf given in days. The gestation rate might differ between breeds due to different reproductive performances.

Box 4: Calving intervals and gestation rate of different cattle breeds for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

For Austria, we obtained the calving interval for several breeds as shown in Table 2 from the standard gross margin catalogue (BAB, 2022). Therefore, the gestation rate can be calculated per cattle breed and can be weighted according to the proportion of breeds in the farm herd.

Table 2: Calving interval (BAB, 2022) and gestation rate per year for different cattle breeds.

Breed	Calving interval (days)	Gestation rate
Fleckvieh	391.3	0.93
Braunvieh	417.5	0.87
Pinzgauer	401.6	0.91
Grauvieh	399.0	0.91
Holstein Friesian	413.8	0.88

- For young cattle up to the age of 1 year, the **weaning age of calves (days)** is relevant because it is assumed that prior to weaning, calves do not emit CH₄ as they are fed with milk.
- For all cattle livestock sub-categories, information on the **feeding situation** is needed. The feeding situation determines how much energy animals need to acquire food, shelter or water, and is relevant for calculating the net energy requirement for activity for cattle (eq. (9)). The IPCC provides activity coefficients for different feeding situations of cattle as summarized in Table 7. The feeding situation is tightly connected to the **grazing strategies** of a farm.

Box 5: Querying farm-level data on grazing livestock for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the application examples of the DFEMS, farmers are asked to indicate whether and which livestock sub-categories they keep on pastures including information on the type of pasture, e.g., alpine pastures. In addition, we ask how many days per year and hours per day animals spend on pastures. This allows us to weight the annual activity coefficient accordingly based on the feeding situation.

Specific activity and performance data requirements for swine farms

In addition to the data required for all livestock sub-categories, specific activity and performance data are required from swine farms:

- The **number of gestations per sow per year** (NumberAnnualGestations(T), in number animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) is needed for breeding sows to derive the average metabolizable energy requirements for maintenance per year as well as for the lactation period. From the number of gestations per year, the length of a gestation period (GestationLength(T), days) can be derived by

$$\text{GestationLength}(T) = \frac{365}{\text{NumberAnnualGestations}(T)} \text{ if } T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\} \quad (5)$$

(own calculation).

- The **litter size per gestation** (LitterSize(T)) is the average number of piglets born and raised (i.e., born piglets minus losses during the suckling period).

Specific activity and performance data requirements for poultry farms

In addition to the performance data that is required for all livestock sub-categories, i.e., data on the production period and on the livestock weights, additional data is required from poultry farms with laying hens:

- For laying hens, the average **daily egg mass production** (EggProd(T); g animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is needed for calculating the N retention rate.

3.1.3. Livestock feeding

The feed intake of livestock is the basis for the production of livestock products such as milk, meat, and eggs. However, the conversion of a feed ration's GE content (in mega joules (MJ)) into energy that can be taken up by the animal for maintenance, growth or offspring production is not completely efficient. As a result of the enteric fermentation, CH₄ is produced and consequently CH₄ and N₂O emissions from manure management and N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils, i.e., emissions occurring after the application of manure on the field. The level of non-CO₂ GHG emissions depends largely on the feed composition and intake.

Figure 1 provides a schematic overview on relevant energy fractions and energy losses, resulting in non-CO₂ GHG emissions. In general, the metabolizable energy (ME; in MJ) is used as the energy unit for assessing the energy requirements for all livestock sub-categories (i.e., cattle, swine and poultry) except for dairy and suckling cows. For dairy cows and suckling cows, the net energy (NE; in MJ) is

used for further non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting. However, in this protocol, we follow the equations for calculating the NE for all cattle sub-categories provided by the IPCC (IPCC, 2019). The energy demands of swine and poultry livestock sub-categories are assessed in ME units.

Figure 1: Schematic overview on energy losses in animal metabolism (adopted from Weiß et al., 2011).

Detailed information on feed rations by livestock sub-category is therefore key for an accurate calculation of non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level. The key feed-related parameters used for calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions include:

- **Feed digestibility** (digestible energy; DE; %) as the fraction of GE not excreted for each defined livestock sub-category in percent;
- **Crude protein content** (CP; %) of the feed ration for each defined livestock sub-category;
- **Crude ash content** (CA; %) of the feed ration for each defined livestock sub-category. The CA of a feed ration influences the excretion of volatile solids (VS), which in turn influence CH₄ emissions from manure management.

Information on the CP content of single feed components as well as conversion factors between fresh and dry matter can be found in comprehensive feed tables provided by the Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft (LfL, 2021a, 2023) and the Landwirtschaftskammer Oberösterreich (LK Oberösterreich; 2020). The CA content of single feed components is primarily derived from [Beweka Rohstofflexikon](#) (2023), an online feed lexicon, and complemented with values provided by Weiß et al. (2011). In addition, INRA-CIRAD-AFZ (French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment, French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development, and Association française de zootechnie; 2021) provides information on the DE of individual feed components. In order to derive the DE of a feed ration, we add the DE of the individual feed components according to their shares in the feed ration. The additive calculation approach of the feed ration's DE does not account for the interactions between nutrients, e.g., with fibre-rich feed components. However, according to the literature (Schug, 2005) and information provided by an expert in the field of animal husbandry and animal nutrition, the additive calculation provides reliable results on the total DE of a feed ration. A full list of considered feed components and the nutritional information is provided in Appendix 2 of the protocol.

Box 6: Querying feed rations for the application examples of the DFEMS in Austria

In the DFEMS, we query a feed ration for each prior defined livestock sub-category. Year-round feed rations, summer and winter feed rations are differentiated. This is relevant, for example, if animals are kept on pastures for a certain time of the year or are fed with fresh feed which is not available throughout the year. Moreover, for swine and poultry, we allow farmers to differentiate between 1-phase, 2-phase, 3-phase, and multi-phase feeding and ask them to provide the feeding ration including the shares of each feeding component for each feeding phase. We assume that the queried feed rations meet the energy and nutrient requirements of a livestock sub-category. Querying the fed feed rations per livestock sub-category at the farm level allows us to account for different farm management and feeding practices and replace the standard values for energy and

nutrient contents of feed components in the calculation equations, as provided by the IPCC (2019, tab. 10.2).

The information on the nutrient content of feed rations or of different feed components, i.e., CP, CA, and DE, is derived from feed analyses done by laboratories. Farmers with available laboratory results can directly enter these values of a feed ration in the respective query field. For farmers who do not have this information at hand, we query the composition of the feed ration per livestock sub-category via the proportions of individual feed components. This facilitates the farm data entering process and makes the DFEMS broadly applicable. The individual feed components are linked to feed tables containing nutritional information on CP, CA, and DE. We then determine the nutritional content of the total feed rations using the proportion of each feed component in the feed ration.

Specific feeding data requirements for swine farms

Low-protein feed rations and phase feeding, i.e., adapting the feed ration to weight ranges in order to meet the animals' nutrient requirements, are important levers for reducing the N-content in manure excreta and therefore direct and indirect N₂O as well as NH₃ emissions. Therefore, the following information on the feeding situation should be collected for calculating the non-CO₂ GHG emissions from swine:

- For fattening pigs, the **number of feeding phases** during the fattening period and therefore the feed ration might differ between farms.
- Information on **N-reduced feeding** differentiated between standard, N-reduced and highly N-reduced feeding rations provides information whether fattening pigs are fed a low-protein feed ration (see Table 3).
- Information on the use of **feed additives** is relevant for fattening pigs.
- Information whether pregnant and lactating breeding sows receive the same feed ration.
- Information whether pregnant and non-pregnant breeding sows receive the same feed ration.

Specific feeding data requirements for poultry farms

In addition to the detailed information on feed rations per poultry sub-category, the following information on the feeding situation and strategy should be collected for calculating the non-CO₂ GHG emissions from poultry:

- For broiler chicken, the **number of feeding phases** during the fattening period might differ between farms.
- Information on whether a farm follows an **N-reduced feeding** strategy.
- Information on the use of **feed additives** in a feed ration.
- The type of the **housing system** has an impact on the energy required for maintenance. To account for the differences at the farm level, information is needed on how the different poultry sub-categories are kept, differentiating between
 - o Floor housing systems
 - o Free range systems

Box 7: The use of pre-defined feed rations for the application examples of the DFEMS in Austria

For Austria, a database containing a total of 278 feed components is stored in the data query tool and used to query feed rations per livestock sub-category at the farm level (see Appendix 2). Moreover, we have pre-defined standard feed rations for each livestock sub-category that are stored in the data query tool. The pre-defined feed rations within the DFEMS serve farmers to enter the feed rations. Farmers are flexible to modify the pre-defined feed rations to their farm-specific needs (see Appendix 3), i.e., users of the data query tool may change the shares of individual feed components and add or remove specific feed components. Farmers can create and save individual

feed rations as well as adjust the nutritional information (CP, CA, DE) of feed components if farm-specific information from feed analyses is available.

The pre-defined feed rations for the application in the DFEMS are derived from the literature and are determined by the (i) nutritional requirements of livestock sub-categories (energy demand of lactating (MJ NEL) and non-lactating (MJ ME) animals as well as the CP demand) and (ii) livestock performance (e.g., daily milk production (in kg animal⁻¹) for dairy cows, daily weight gain (in g animal⁻¹) for beef cattle and broilers). Restrictions on feed intake, such as physiological upper limits of different livestock sub-categories for certain feed components (e.g., crude fibre, crude fat) are accounted for in the feed rations. These feed rations consist of roughage and concentrated feed and are composed, for example, of hay, grass silage, maize silage, and mineral feed. In addition to different crop types and conservation methods, different feed qualities are accounted for, depending on, e.g., the mowing frequency. This is reflected in the different CP contents of respective feed components.

Bellof and Granz (2019) provide exemplary feed rations for dairy cows with different production levels (kg milk animal⁻¹ year⁻¹), fattening bulls and heifers (weight gain in g animal⁻¹ day⁻¹). The pre-defined feed rations for cattle sub-categories are based on examples provided in the [standard gross margin catalogue](#) (BAB, 2022) and by the LfL (2021a, 2023).

The pre-defined feed rations for swine sub-categories are divided into standard and N-reduced feed rations. Additionally, highly N-reduced feed rations are available for fattening pigs. N-reduced and highly N-reduced feeding rations can be applied for single-phase as well as multi-phase feeding strategies. Well-defined limits of nitrogen in N-reduced and highly N-reduced feed rations (Table 3) for swine sub-categories are used according to the Austrian guidelines for fertilization in crop and grassland (Richtlinien für die sachgerechte Düngung im Ackerbau und Grünland; BMLRT, 2022) and the Austrian agri-environmental programme OePUL (AMA, 2023). To appropriately account for N-reduction and nutritional needs, the fattening period is split into three phases, i.e., beginning, middle, and end of the fattening period. Standard feed rations for fattening pigs are sourced from Weiß et al. (2011), while N-reduced and highly N-reduced feed rations are based on Weber (2021) and Preißinger et al. (2018).

Table 3: Upper limits for the crude protein content (CP; g per kg dry matter) in N-reduced and highly N-reduced swine feed rations (AMA, 2023; BMLRT, 2022).

Feeding strategy	Livestock sub-category	Upper CP limit (g)
N-reduced feeding	piglets 8 – 32 kg	170
	Breeding sows, empty	150
	Breeding sows, gestation	130
	Breeding sows, lactation	165
	Fattening pigs 32 – 70 kg	170
	Fattening pigs from 32 kg	161
	Fattening pigs from 70 kg	155
Highly N-reduced feeding	Fattening pigs 32 – 60 kg	170
	Fattening pigs 60 to 90 kg	155
	Fattening pigs from 32 kg	157
	Fattening pigs from 90 kg	150

3.2. Methane emission calculation from enteric fermentation

Following the tier 2 approach, the CH₄ emission factor, and, therefore, CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation are based on the feed intake (IPCC, 2019), which is typically given in gross energy (GE; MJ day⁻¹) or dry matter (DM; kg day⁻¹), as well as on a livestock sub-category-specific CH₄ conversion factor (Y_m).

Box 8: Approach for calculating emissions from enteric fermentation for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the DFEMS, we apply the approach based on GE and use the farm-level data described in section 3.1 to calculate CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation based on the livestock

performance-specific energy requirements for the different livestock sub-categories. We calculate the CH₄ emission factor for each defined livestock sub-category.

The general equation for calculating the CH₄ emission factor ($EF_{CH_4,EntFerm}(T)$; kg CH₄ animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) from enteric fermentation for the livestock sub-category T is given by

$$EF_{CH_4,EntFerm}(T) = \frac{GE(T) * \left(\frac{Y_m(T)}{100}\right) * 365}{55.65} \quad (6)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.21), where $Y_m(T)$ is the CH₄ conversion factor, i.e., a percentage of the GE in the feed that is converted to CH₄, and 55.65 is the energy content of CH₄ in MJ per kg CH₄. The CH₄ emission factor is derived at an annual basis, i.e., 365 days. If livestock sub-categories are fed a mixture of a summer and winter feed ration or feeding situations vary within a year, i.e., livestock is kept on pastures for a certain period, the emission factor is to be estimated for the specific period by replacing the 365 by the weight of a certain feed ration in the annual feed ration, and then summed over the respective periods. Thereby, the weight of a feed ration can be defined as the number of days a certain feeding ration is fed or the number of days (hours) per year, livestock is kept on pastures.

In order to derive total farm-level CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation ($CH_4_{Total,EntFerm}$), the $EF_{CH_4,EntFerm}(T)$ must be multiplied by the annual average number of animals per livestock sub-category and summed across all livestock sub-categories kept on the farm:

$$CH_4_{Total,EntFerm} = \sum_T (EF_{CH_4,EntFerm}(T) * AAP(T)) \quad (7)$$

(IPCC, 2019), where $AAP(T)$ is the average annual population of animals of a livestock sub-category T (see eq. (1)). For livestock sub-categories that are kept at the farm a full year, i.e., 365 days, $AAP(T)$ equals $livestock_{count}(T)$ (e.g., for dairy cows, suckling cows, breeding sows, boars).

The IPCC (2019) provides values of Y_m for cattle. These values differ depending on the livestock sub-category, the DE in combination with the share of neutral detergent fibre (NDF) in the DM of the feed ration, the annual milk production for dairy cows, and the feed composition, i.e., the percentage of forage in a feed ration, for non-dairy and multi-purpose cattle sub-categories. Table 4 summarizes these values for cattle.

Table 4: Methane conversion factors ($Y_m(T)$) by cattle sub-category (IPCC, 2019; tab. 10.12)

Livestock sub-category	Description	DE (%) Neutral Detergent Fibre; NDF (% of DM)	Methane conversion factor, Y_m (%)
Dairy cows	> 8500 kg milk per animal and year	DE ≥ 70 NDF ≤ 35	5.7
	> 8500 kg milk per animal and year	DE ≥ 70 NDF ≥ 35	6.0
	5000 – 8000 kg milk per animal and year	DE 63-70 NDF >37	6.3
	<5000 kg milk per animal and year	DE ≤ 62 NDF > 38	6.5
Non-dairy and multi-purpose cattle	> 75 % forage	DE ≤ 62	7.0
	Rations of > 75% high quality forage and/or mixed rations, forage of between 15 and 75%	DE 62 – 71	6.3

the total ration mixed with grain, and/or silage		
Feedlots (all other grains, 0-15% forage)	DE >= 72	4.0
Feedlot (steam-flaked corn; 0-10% forage)	DE >= 75	3.0

Box 9: Methane conversion factors ($Y_m(T)$) used for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the DFEMS, we apply the values of Y_m for cattle as provided by the IPCC (see Table 4) for the prior defined cattle sub-categories. For swine and poultry, Austrian's National Inventory Report (Anderl et al., 2023b) provides national values of Y_m which are applied in the DFEMS (Table 5).

Table 5: Methane conversion factors for swine and poultry by livestock sub-category (Anderl et al., 2023b; Table 8)

Livestock (sub-)category	Methane conversion factor, $Y_m(T)$ (%)
Breeding sows	0.71
Fattening pigs	0.46
Piglets	0.44
Poultry	0.16

In general, the energy requirements (ME and NE, respectively) comprise requirements for maintenance, activity and growth, performance-related requirements (i.e., for meat, milk, egg production) as well as requirements to produce offspring (gestation). In order to derive the GE, the total energy requirements (ME and NE, respectively) are calculated in the first step for each livestock sub-category. The IPCC (2019) provides equations for calculating NE intake ($\text{MJ animal}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) for key ruminant categories such as cattle. However, the IPCC (2019, 2006) does not provide equations for estimating energy requirements for the livestock sub-categories of swine and poultry. Approaches for deriving the energy requirements of swine and poultry are available in the literature and are used in the DFEMS for non- CO_2 GHG emission accounting at the farm level.

In the second step, the actual conversion from NE and ME to GE is done. For cattle, energy availability characteristics and nutritional information of the feed rations are used to convert from NE to GE. For swine and poultry, we assume a standard conversion factor for converting the ME to GE (see Section 3.2.2 and 3.2.3).

The following sub-sections describe how to derive the farm- and livestock sub-category-specific GE to be applied in eq. (6).

3.2.1. Energy requirements of cattle

The energy requirements of cattle are calculated by adding the energy needed for maintenance, growth and activity, and for producing offspring following the IPCC equations (IPCC, 2019; see step (i)); this approach can be applied in the DFEMS, using farm-level data. Next, the energy availability ratio for maintenance and growth are calculated which are then used for converting the NE to GE as a final step.

Step (i) energy requirements of cattle sub-categories

The **net energy required for maintenance** ($\text{NE}_m(T)$; $\text{MJ animal}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) is given for each cattle sub-category by

$$\text{NE}_m(T) = C_i * (\text{Weight}(T))^{0.75} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{cattle}\} \quad (8)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.3), where C_i is the coefficient for calculating the net energy for maintenance and $\text{Weight}(T)$ is the live weight of a typical animal in the cattle sub-category T in kg. The coefficient C_i is

different for lactating cattle, non-lactating cattle, and bulls, and is given in MJ kg⁻¹ day⁻¹. Table 6 summarizes the maintenance coefficients that are used in the DFEMS for calculating the net energy required for maintenance for cattle.

Table 6: Maintenance coefficient by cattle sub-categories (adopted from IPCC, 2019; tab. 10.4)

Livestock sub-category	Maintenance coefficient, C _i (MJ kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)
All non-lactating cows, steers, heifers and calves	0.322
Lactating cows	0.386
Bulls	0.37

The required **net energy for activity** (NE_a(T); MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹), i.e., the additional energy needed for acquiring food, water or shelter, is a function of NE_m(T) and can be calculated for each cattle sub-category T with

$$NE_a(T) = C_a * NE_m(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{cattle}\} \quad (9)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.4), where C_a is the activity coefficient depending on the livestock feeding situation. Table 7 summarizes the activity coefficients for livestock confined in a stall, for livestock on pastures, and for livestock grazing large areas. Calculating NE_a(T) for a mixture of several feeding situations within a year, e.g., livestock on pastures during summer and livestock confined in a stall during winter, requires weighting according to the share (i.e., number of days or hours, respectively) of each feeding situation in the total year (see Section 3.1.2).

Table 7: Activity coefficients corresponding to feeding situations of cattle (IPCC, 2019; tab. 10.5)

Feeding situation	Definition	Activity coefficient, C _a (dimensionless)
Stall	Animals are confined to a small area (i.e., tethered, pen, barn) requiring very little or no energy to acquire feed.	0
Pasture	Animals are confined in areas with sufficient forage requiring modest energy to acquire feed.	0.17
Grazing large areas	Animals graze in open range land or hilly terrain and expend significant energy to acquire feed.	0.36

Growing animals, i.e., young cattle, breeding and fattening cattle, require energy for gaining weight. The required **net energy for growth** (NE_g(T); MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) for the respective cattle sub-categories T is given by

$$NE_g(T) = 22.02 * \left(\frac{\text{Weight}(T)}{C_{\text{growth}}(T) * LW_{\text{mature}}(T)} \right)^{0.75} * (\text{WG}(T))^{1.097} \quad (10)$$

if T ∈ {young cattle up to 1 year, young cattle 1 – 2 years, breeding and fattening cattle}

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.5), where C_{growth}(T) is the growth coefficient for cattle, LW_{mature}(T) is the mature live weight of a typical animal in the livestock sub-category T in kg, and WG(T) is the average weight gain of the animal in kg per day. The available growth coefficients are summarized in Table 8 and depend on the sex of the animal, offering different values for female cattle, castrates, and bulls.

Table 8: Growth coefficients by cattle sub-categories (IPCC, 2019, p. 10.24)

Cattle sub-category	Growth coefficient, C _{growth} (T) (dimensionless)
Female cattle	0.8
Castrates	1.0

The required **net energy for lactation** ($NE_l(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) needs to be calculated for dairy cows and suckling cows and depends on the average daily milk production and the milk quality, i.e., the milk fat content, as given by

$$NE_l(T) = \text{MilkProduction}(T) * (1.47 + 0.40 * \text{MilkFat}) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (11)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.8), where $\text{MilkProduction}(T)$ is the average daily milk production in kg per animal and day, 1.47 and 0.4 are constants, and MilkFat is the milk fat content in %. $\text{MilkProduction}(T)$ can be determined by applying eq. (2) or eq. (3).

The additionally required **net energy for gestation (pregnancy)** ($NE_p(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) of dairy cows and suckling cows is a fraction of their required net energy for maintenance and is given by

$$NE_p(T) = C_p * NE_m(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (12)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.13), where C_p is the gestation coefficient. For cattle, the additionally required net energy for gestation is assumed to be 10% of $NE_m(T)$, i.e., the gestation coefficient is 0.1. Similar to $NE_a(T)$, $NE_p(T)$ at the farm level has to be weighted according to the actual proportion of dairy cows and suckling cows, respectively, that go through a gestation in one year.

The required additional **net energy for work** purposes can – in the case of Austria – be assumed to be zero since cattle is not used as draft animals anymore.

Step (ii) energy availability in livestock feed for cattle livestock sub-categories

For cattle, the ratio of net energy available in a diet, i.e., through feeding a certain feed ration, for maintenance to digestible energy available in a given feed ration (REM, dimensionless) is expressed as

$$\text{REM} = \left(1.123 - (4.092 * 10^{-3} * \text{DE}) + (1.126 * 10^{-5} * \text{DE}^2) - \left(\frac{25.4}{\text{DE}} \right) \right) \quad (13)$$

if $T \in \{\text{cattle}\}$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.14). To account for different feeding strategies and qualities of feed components, we use the feed ration-specific DE in the DFEMS (see Section 3.1.3).

The ratio of net energy available in a diet for growth to digestible energy consumed (REG, dimensionless) is given by

$$\text{REG} = 1.164 - (5.16 * 10^{-3} * \text{DE}) + (1.308 * 10^{-5} * (\text{DE})^2) - \left(\frac{37.4}{\text{DE}} \right) \quad (14)$$

if $T \in \{\text{cattle}\}$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.15). Again, different feeding strategies can be accounted for by using the farm-specific DE of a feed ration.

Step (iii) gross energy intake of cattle livestock sub-categories

Using all these NE and ME components and the energy availability in the feed rations, the total gross energy intake ($GE(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) for each cattle sub-category is given by

$$GE(T) = \left(\frac{\frac{NE_m(T) + NE_a(T) + NE_l(T) + NE_p(T)}{REM} + \frac{NE_g(T)}{REG}}{DE} \right) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{cattle}\} \quad (15)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.15). Only those terms in the equation that are relevant for the respective cattle livestock sub-category are used, i.e., for calculating the GE of e.g., dairy cows, the term $NE_g(T)$ is omitted since we do not account for any weight gains and assume that no energy is required for growth.

3.2.2. Energy requirements of swine

The equations for deriving the energy requirements for swine sub-categories are differentiated for the livestock sub-categories of breeding sows, piglets and fattening pigs as well as breeding boars. The determination of the energy requirements (step (i)) is therefore presented below according to this differentiation.

Step (i) energy requirements of swine livestock sub-categories

Energy requirements of breeding sows

For breeding sows, energy requirements comprise the energy required for maintenance and performance, i.e., the energy requirements during lactation.

The required **metabolizable energy for maintenance** ($ME_m(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_m(T) = \sum_{BP} C_{i,BP} * (\text{Weight}(T))^{0.75} * \frac{\text{days}_{BP}(T)}{\text{GestLength}(T)} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\} \quad (16)$$

(van der Peet-Schwering and Bikker, 2019), where $C_{i,BP}$ is the maintenance coefficient in MJ per kg live weight and day for a specific breeding phase BP, $\text{days}_{BP}(T)$ is the length of a breeding phase in days, and $\text{GestLength}(T)$ is the total length of the gestation period in days, i.e., the sum over the gestation, lactation, and empty phase. $C_{i,BP}$ differs between the gestation, lactation, and empty period (Table 9). In order to derive the average ME_m per breeding sow and day, we weight the energy requirements for maintenance by the number of days the breeding sow is in a certain breeding phase and sum over all breeding phases.

Table 9: Maintenance coefficient and length per breeding phase for breeding sows (van der Peet-Schwering and Bikker, 2019)

Breeding phase, BP	Maintenance coefficient, $C_{i,BP}$ (MJ kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	Length of breeding phase, $\text{days}_{BP}(T)$ (days)
Gestation	0.44	115*
Lactation	0.46	20
Empty	0.44	$\text{GestLength}(T) - 115 - 20^*$

* see eq. (5) for the farm-specific gestation length

The required **metabolizable energy for performance** (ME_p ; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is the energy that a breeding sow requires during the lactation period. It is calculated from the energy required by the piglets for maintenance and growth, i.e., the energy provided by the mother sow via the milk, and is given by

$$ME_p(T) = \frac{\left(0.44 * (\text{Weight}(\text{piglets}))^{0.75} + \frac{0.0395 * \text{WG}_{\text{fat}}^{LS}(T) + 0.0238 * \text{WG}_{\text{protein}}^{LS}(T)}{0.78} \right) * \text{LitterSize}(T)}{0.93} \quad (17)$$

if $T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\}$

(van der Peet-Schwering and Bikker, 2019), where the first part of the numerator, i.e., $0.44 * (\text{Weight}(\text{piglets}))^{0.75}$, is the required metabolizable energy for maintenance of a suckling piglet and the

second part of the numerator is the metabolizable energy required for growth of a suckling piglet. Thereof, $WG_{fat}^{LS}(T)$ and $WG_{protein}^{LS}(T)$ is the fat and protein deposition of suckling piglets in g per kg daily weight gain, i.e., the ratio of fat and protein gain to weight gain, respectively. The constant 0.0395 is the energy content (MJ) of 1 g fat and 0.0238 is the energy content of protein in MJ per g protein. The constant 0.78 is the partial efficiency of ME in milk for daily gain in MJ per MJ. Moreover, $LitterSize(T)$ is the litter size, i.e., the number of suckling piglets per gestation, and as $LitterSize(T)$ is subject to the production intensity and can vary between farms, we query this information at the farm level. 0.93 is the metabolizable energy of milk; a product of the energy digestibility of milk and the ratio between digestible and metabolizable energy (CVB, 2018; Evers et al. 1995, in Van Der Peet-Schwering and Bikker, 2019).

Box 10: Default values for the litter size of a breeding sow for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

If farm-level information is not available on the litter size, we obtained the default values for different production intensities as shown in Table 10 from the standard gross margin catalogue (BAB, 2022).

Table 10: Litter size of a breeding sow for different production intensities (BAB, 2022).

Production intensity	Litter size (born piglets per gestation)
high	13.1
medium	12.3
low	11.5

The fat and protein deposition ($WG_{fat}^{LS}(T)$, $WG_{protein}^{LS}(T)$, g (kg daily weight gain)⁻¹) can be derived from the average daily weight gain of the piglet, i.e., $WG(T)$ in kg per day. In the DFEMS we, therefore, use the equations provided by van der Peet-Schwering and Bikker (2019) to derive WG_{fat}^{LS} and $WG_{protein}^{LS}$:

$$WG_{fat}^{LS}(T) = WG(T) * (135 + 140 * WG(T)) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{piglet} < 8 \text{ kg}\} \quad (18)$$

$$WG_{protein}^{LS}(T) = 160 * WG(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{piglet} < 8 \text{ kg}\} \quad (19)$$

Energy requirements of piglets and fattening pigs

For piglets and fattening pigs, the increase in protein and fat during growth requires an adequate supply of energy, both for maintenance and growth. Regardless of the growth stage, the required **metabolizable energy for maintenance** ($ME_m(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_m(T) = 0.44 * (\text{Weight}(T))^{0.75} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (20)$$

(Jeroch et al., 2020) where 0.44 is again the maintenance coefficient. This approach allows to account for different feeding phases, i.e., defining the livestock sub-categories for fattening pigs based on the feeding phase.

The required **energy for performance** ($ME_g(T)$; MJ animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) results from the fat and protein deposition of fattening pigs and is given by

$$ME_g(T) = WG(T) * \frac{39.7 * WG_{fat}(T)}{0.74} + \frac{23.8 * WG_{protein}(T)}{0.56} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (21)$$

(Haenel et al., 2011; Jeroch et al., 2020), where $WG(T)$ is the daily weight gain in kg. $WG_{fat}(T)$ and $WG_{protein}(T)$ are the ratio of fat and protein gain to weight gain in g per kg weight gain for a specific growth phase, respectively. 39.7 and 23.8 are constants for the energy content in fat and protein in MJ

per kg fat and protein, respectively. The constants 0.74 and 0.56 are partial efficiencies for the fat and protein gain.

The $WG_{fat}(T)$ and $WG_{protein}(T)$ ($kg\ kg^{-1}$) in turn depend on the live weight. Whereas $WG_{fat}(T)$ increases with increasing live weight, $WG_{protein}(T)$ decreases with increasing live weight. $WG_{fat}(T)$ and $WG_{protein}(T)$ can be derived as follows

$$WG_{fat}(T) = 0.94 * 0.1166 + 0.002778 * Weight(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (22)$$

$$WG_{protein}(T) = 0.168 - 0.0001828 * Weight(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (23)$$

(eq. (8) and (9) from GfE, 2006 differentiated with respect to animal weight; see also Haenel et al., 2011; Jeroch et al., 2020), where 0.1166 and 0.168 are constants in kg per kg live weight, 0.002778 and 0.0001828 are constants in kg per animal, 0.94 is the correction factor for deriving the animals' live weight minus the entire content of the stomach, intestines, and bladder.

Figure 2: Change in the ratio of fat and protein gain to weight gain ($g\ kg^{-1}$) at different live weights (kg) of piglets and fattening pigs (adapted from Jeroch et al., 2020, p. 397; cited after GfE, 2006).

Energy requirements of breeding boars

Equivalent to piglets and fattening pigs, the energy requirements for breeding boars comprise requirements for maintenance and growth. The currently available literature does not provide detailed information on the calculation of daily metabolic energy requirements (ME_{total}) of breeding boars. We decided to apply $35\ MJ\ animal^{-1}\ day^{-1}$, as suggested by Haenel et al. (2011) and Jeroch et al. (2020) due to the low relevance of breeding boars in Austria.

Step (ii) gross energy intake of swine sub-categories

In animal nutrition, the ratio between metabolizable energy (ME) and the gross energy (GE), i.e., $ME * GE^{-1}$, is expressed as percentage and called convertibility of energy. The percentage of ME in GE is influenced by the livestock category and the characteristics of the feed ration, particularly the digestibility. Feed rations with a high DE value, as is the case for swine, have an average metabolizability/convertibility of 75-80%. This is therefore considerably higher than for ruminants (around 60%), which is due to a lower DE as well as higher gas losses in form of methane.

The conversion from ME to GE for swine must therefore be corrected by the factor $100 * 80^{-1} = 1.25$.

3.2.3. Energy requirements of poultry

Calculations of energy requirements of poultry are differentiated for the livestock sub-categories laying hens and pullets and broilers. Equivalent to cattle and swine, the feed intake requirements can be derived by summing the metabolizable energy requirements for maintenance and performance. For laying hens, the metabolizable energy for growth is added in addition.

Step (i) energy requirements of poultry livestock sub-categories

Energy requirements for laying hens and pullets

For laying hens, the required **metabolizable energy for maintenance** ($ME_m(T)$; MJ ME animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_m(T) = C_f * (\text{Weight}(T))^{0.75} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{laying hens, pullets}\} \quad (24)$$

(Gierus, 2021; Schreiter and Damme, 2017), where C_f is the maintenance coefficient. The maintenance coefficient depends on the type of housing system. In cage systems (battery cages; no longer permitted in Austria; 1. Tierhaltungsverordnung, 2005 i.d.F. vom 27.07.2022), it is 0.48. In floor and free-range housing systems, the metabolizable energy requirement for maintenance is 10% and 15% higher due to the different movement possibilities and energy required for heat regulation and feed intake (Jeroch et al., 2020), i.e., 0.528 and 0.552 respectively.

The required **metabolizable energy for performance** ($ME_p(T)$; MJ ME animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_p(T) = 0.0096 * \text{EggProd}(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{laying hens}\} \quad (25)$$

(Jeroch et al., 2020; Schreiter and Damme, 2017), where $\text{EggProd}(T)$ is the daily egg mass production in grams per animal and 0.0096 is a constant, defined as the ratio of the energy content of the produced egg mass (i.e., 0.0065 MJ g⁻¹) to the partial efficiency of produced egg mass (68%) and given in MJ per g produced egg mass.

During the first four weeks of laying, laying hens have not reached their mature weight. Therefore, they have an additional need of **metabolizable energy for growth** ($ME_g(T)$; MJ ME animal⁻¹ day⁻¹), which is given by

$$ME_g(T) = 0.023 * \text{WG}(T) * \frac{28}{365} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{laying hens}\} \quad (26)$$

(Gierus, 2021; Schreiter and Damme, 2017), where 0.023 is the growth coefficient and $\text{WG}(T)$ the daily weight gain in grams per animal. According to Schreiter and Damme (2017), the energy requirement for growth, i.e., for the increase in live weight, is taken into account from the 18th week of life (time of housing in) until the 32nd week of life and is negligible thereafter.

Energy requirements for broilers

For broilers, the required **metabolizable energy for maintenance** ($ME_m(T)$; in MJ ME animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_m(T) = 0.48 * (\text{Weight}(T))^{0.75} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{broiler chickens}\} \quad (27)$$

and the required **net energy for performance** (ME_p ; MJ ME animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$ME_p(T) = \frac{0.03977 * \text{WG}_{\text{fat}}(T)}{0.84} + \frac{0.02386 * \text{WG}_{\text{protein}}(T)}{0.52} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{broiler chickens}\} \quad (28)$$

(Jeroch et al., 2020; Weiß et al., 2011), where 0.03977 and 0.02386 are constants for the energy content in fat and protein, $\text{WG}_{\text{fat}}(T)$ and $\text{WG}_{\text{protein}}(T)$ is the fat and protein disposition of broilers and 0.84 and 0.52 are the partial efficiencies for the fat and protein gain.

The fat ($WG_{\text{fat}}(T)$) and protein deposition ($WG_{\text{protein}}(T)$) in broilers change over the course of growth and differ between the sexes (Jeroch et al., 2020, p. 640; Tab. 31.42). Since farm data collection is not possible to such a degree, the following equations can be applied to derive $WG_{\text{fat}}(T)$ and $WG_{\text{protein}}(T)$ (g kg^{-1}):

$$WG_{\text{fat}}(T) = 16.844 * \frac{WG(T)}{100} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{broiler chickens}\} \quad (29)$$

$$WG_{\text{protein}}(T) = (3.125 + 16.075) * \frac{WG(T)}{100} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{broiler chickens}\} \quad (30)$$

(Jeroch et al., 2020; Weiß et al., 2011), where $WG(T)$ is the average daily weight gain in g, 16.844 is the fat deposition per 100 g weight gain, and 3.125 and 16.075 is the protein deposition in feathers and the animal's body per 100 g weight gain.

Step (ii) gross energy intake of poultry sub-categories

In animal nutrition, the ratio between metabolizable energy (ME) and the gross energy (GE), i.e., $ME * GE^{-1}$, is expressed as percentage and called convertibility of energy. The percentage of ME in GE is influenced by the livestock category and the characteristics of the feed ration, particularly the digestibility. Feed rations with a high DE value, as is the case for poultry, have an average metabolizability/convertibility of 75-80%. This is therefore considerably higher than for ruminants (around 60%), which is due to a lower DE as well as higher gas losses in form of CH_4 (personal communication, 2024).

The conversion from ME to GE for poultry must therefore be corrected by the factor $100 * 80^{-1} = 1.25$.

3.3. Calculation of methane, nitrous oxide, and ammonia emissions from manure management

Non-CO₂ emissions from manure management are produced during the handling and storage of livestock manure. The term “manure” includes both the liquid and solid, i.e., dung and urine, produced by livestock (IPCC, 2019). The non-CO₂ GHG emissions calculated in this chapter are limited to those non-CO₂ emissions occurring before the manure is applied to soils or used for other purposes such as fuel or construction.

The main factors affecting CH₄ emissions from manure management are (1) the amount of manure produced by livestock which in turn is linked to the number of animals and their rate of manure production, and (2) the proportion of manure that decomposes in the absence of oxygen. The amount of CH₄ produced is additionally influenced by the temperature and the duration of storage within a manure storage system.

Direct and indirect N₂O emissions from manure management occur during the storage and treatment of the manure. Direct N₂O emissions result from nitrification and denitrification processes of N contained in the manure. The amount of direct N₂O emissions depends on the N and carbon (C) content of the manure. Similarly, the amount of CH₄ emissions depends on the duration of the manure storage and type of treatment. Volatile N losses, in the form of NH₃ and NO_x, contribute to indirect N₂O emissions. Such N losses start from the point of livestock manure excretions and continue through manure storage and management at the farm. N losses due to run-off and leaching into the soil from stored manure or from areas with grazing livestock also contribute to indirect N₂O emissions. Dung and urine that is deposited on pastures during grazing by livestock is reported under the category “Nitrous oxide emissions from managed agricultural soils” (see section 47) because the generated N₂O emissions occur directly and indirectly from the soil.

3.3.1. Manure management related farm-level input data

In Austria, 15.2% of the total non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agriculture are generated during manure management (Anderl et al., 2023b). For accurate non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting from manure management at the farm level, we propose to make use of the tier 2 approach, relying on farm-level data on (1) manure characteristics, (2) manure management (i.e., handling and storage) of the livestock manure, and (3) livestock housing systems and grazing situation. Therefore, the following farm-level data are required for calculating the non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level:

- (1) **Manure characteristics** refer to the amount of volatile solids (VS) that an animal excretes (see eq. (32)). VS are defined as “*the organic material in livestock manure and consist of both biodegradable and non-biodegradable fractions*” (IPCC, 2006, p. 10.42). VS will be calculated for each farm individually considering the livestock feed ration characteristics such as DE, GE, and CA (see section 3.1.3 for livestock feeding data requirements).
- (2) The farm-level data on **manure management of livestock manure** includes the following:
 - **Type of manure storage system:** During manure storage, considerable amounts of CH₄, N₂O, and NH₃ are released, depending on the type of manure storage system (Amon et al., 2006; Smith et al., 2008). Therefore, the type of manure storage system is relevant for both potential mitigation measures and the overall mitigation potential (for definitions of manure management systems see table 10.18 in IPCC, 2019 or https://raumberg-gumpenstein.at/jdownloads/Tagungen/Bautagung/Bautagung_2011/3b_2011_doebler.pdf)

Box 11: Manure storage systems considered in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

For the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria, we differentiate the following types of manure storage system when querying farm-level data:

- Manure deposited by grazing livestock on pasture, range, paddock (i.e., amount derived from the number of days per year and hours per day livestock sub-categories are kept on pastures)

- Solid manure storage systems (including solids from manure separation, fermentation residues, dried chicken manure)
- Liquid manure storage systems (i.e., mixture of urine leached from the solid manure and water)
- Slurry manure storage systems (i.e., mixture of faeces and urine produced)
- Anaerobic digester (i.e., agricultural biogas plants)
- Composting
- Aerobic treatment

When querying the capacity utilization of the manure storage systems, we distinguish between storage during summer and winter, which allows us to account for temperature-related differences in emissions (Amon et al., 2007, 2006; Anderl et al., 2023b). If multiple manure storage systems are in place, information about the distribution is needed.

- **Total manure storage volume (m³) and capacity utilization (%) or the actual amount of manure stored in each manure storage system (m³):** The total manure storage volume per manure storage system is used together with the capacity utilization to derive the actually stored amount of manure (m³). Moreover, it can be used as a control variable for the total amount of manure stored depending on the livestock numbers.
- **Manure storage system distribution (%):** The information on the fraction of manure that is handled in a specific manure storage system is relevant if there are multiple manure storage systems at the farm.
- **Manure storage system cover:** Covering manure storage systems is considered an effective measure for reducing non-CO₂ GHG emissions during manure storage – particularly for reducing NH₃ emissions. In slurry and liquid manure storage systems, air exchange with the emitting surface of the manure should be minimized (Anderl et al., 2016). The basic aim is to reduce the surface area of storage systems per unit volume of slurry and liquid manure (Amon et al., 2021; UN/ECE, 1999).

Box 12: Manure storage system covers considered in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

Based on the availability of emission factors, five manure storage cover categories for liquid/slurry manure are distinguished in the DFEMS

- not covered
- natural crust
- permeable straw cover
- floating sheet (plastic sheet)
- fixed cover (concrete, wood, tent)

In addition to these storage cover categories, for solid manure information is required on whether it is

- compacted
- covered
- managed with agent bulking
- managed with additives
- active mixing or no mixing
- composting: intensive/passive windrow, static pile or in-vessel.

- (3) **Livestock housing system and grazing situation**, i.e., how many days a year and how many hours a day livestock is kept on pastures. Through farm-level data on the number of days per year and the hours per day livestock is kept on pastures, the fraction of **manure that is deposited by grazing livestock** can be accounted for, i.e., the share of manure deposited by grazing animals can be derived and subtracted from total annual amount of manure that is produced by livestock

sub-categories. The amount of manure deposited on pastures reduces the amount of manure stored in a specific manure storage system.

3.3.2. Methane emission calculation from manure management

Following the IPCC tier 2 approach, for each defined livestock sub-category T (see Section 3.1), a respective farm-specific CH₄ emission factor (EF_{CH₄,MM}(T); kg CH₄ animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) for emissions from manure management is calculated by

$$EF_{CH_4,MM}(T) = VS(T) * 365 * [B_0(T) * 0.67 * \sum_{S,T} \frac{MCF(S, T)}{100} * MS(S, T)] \quad (31)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.23), where VS(T) is the volatile solid (VS) excreted by the livestock sub-category T in kg DM per animal and day; B₀(T) is the maximum CH₄ producing capacity for manure produced by the livestock sub-category T in m³ CH₄ per kg of VS excreted; 0.67 is the conversion factor from m³ CH₄ to kg CH₄; MCF(S, T) is the methane conversion factor in % for each manure storage system S and livestock sub-category T, and MS(S, T) is the fraction of manure of a livestock sub-category T that is handled in manure storage system S.

VS is the fraction of livestock manure comprised primarily of organic material, with biodegradable and non-biodegradable fractions. VS represents the undigested fraction of the consumed feed that is excreted as faecal material. When combined with urinary excretions, this forms the entirety of the manure (IPCC, 2019). VS can be calculated based on the farm-specific feed intake levels (see section 3.2.1 to 3.2.3) and nutritional information of feed rations for each livestock sub-category. VS(T) (kg DM animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$VS(T) = \left[GE(T) * \left(1 - \frac{DE}{100} \right) + (UE * GE(T)) \right] * \left[\frac{1 - CA}{18.45} \right] \quad (32)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.24), where UE is the urinary energy expressed as a fraction of GE in MJ per day (see also Figure 1), CA is the crude ash content of the feed ration in percent as a fraction of the DMI, and 18.45 is the conversion factor for GE from feed intake in MJ per kg to DMI in MJ. For non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting at the farm level, the feed ration-specific CA value (see section 3.1.3) can be applied. For UE we apply the default value of 0.04 for cattle and poultry in the DFEMS. However, we reduce this value to 0.02 for cattle sub-categories that are fed a feeding ration consisting of 85% or more grain, and for swine (IPCC, 2019).

The B₀(T), i.e., the maximum amount of CH₄ that can be produced from a certain type of manure, varies by livestock (sub-) category and feeding situation. The B₀(T) values are based on the total VS that enter the manure storage system, i.e., both the biodegradable and non-biodegradable fractions. In accordance with Austria's National Inventory Report (Anderl et al., 2023b) and because more refined values are not available, we apply the default values for Western Europe, provided by the IPCC, which are differentiated by livestock (sub-)category (IPCC, 2019; tab. 10.16A). In Table 11, the default B₀(T) values for cattle (dairy and non-dairy), swine, and poultry (laying and other chicken) are summarized that can be applied to farms in Austria.

Table 11: Default B₀(T) values for Western Europe (IPCC, 2019; tab. 10.16A).

Livestock (sub-) category	B ₀ (T) (m ³ CH ₄ /kg VS)
Dairy cows	0.24
Non-dairy cattle	0.18
Swine	0.45
Chicken – Layer	0.39
All other poultry	0.36

The **MCF** states the portion of the maximum CH₄ producing capacity, i.e., B₀(T), that is realized by each type of manure storage system, i.e., how much of the VS(T) is converted to CH₄ (Hung et al., 2022). The MCF depends on the temperature, the type of manure, and how the manure is stored – in particular the type of manure storage cover of slurry manure storage systems. Therefore, the IPCC (2019, 2006) recommends to apply MCFs that represent regional and management-specific conditions. Amon et al. (2007, 2006) show for uncovered slurry manure storage systems that CH₄ emissions are higher during the warm season compared to the cold season and provide country- and season-specific MCFs for slurry manure storage systems for cattle and swine (Table 12). These MCFs are also applied in Austria's National Inventory Report (Anderl et al., 2023b).

Table 12: Country specific MCFs for slurry manure storage systems in Austria (Amon et al., 2007, 2006; Anderl et al., 2023b)

Livestock (sub-) category	MCF(S,T) – cold season (%)	MCF(S,T) – warm seasons (%)	MCF(S,T) – average (%)
Dairy Cattle	-	-	8.8
Other cattle	-	-	8.4
Cattle	0.97	37.22	-
Swine	3.27	3.87	3.4

The type of manure storage cover influences the amount of CH₄ emissions released during manure storage. The queried farm-level data on the type of manure storage cover for slurry manure storage systems allows us to use the refined MCFs in the DFEMS, as provided by the Arbeitsgruppe BEK (2021) and Haenel et al. (2020), given in Table 13. It should be noted that the same MCFs are applied to all livestock sub-categories within a livestock category.

Table 13: Methane conversion factors (MCF) for slurry manure storage systems by livestock category and type of manure storage cover (Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021; Haenel et al., 2020).

Livestock category	Manure storage cover	MCF(S,T) (%)	Source
Cattle	natural crust	10	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Cattle	permeable straw cover	17	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Cattle	floating sheet (plastic sheet)	17	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Cattle	fixed cover (concrete, wood, tent)	17	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Swine	natural crust	15	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)
Swine	permeable straw cover	25	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)
Swine	floating sheet (plastic sheet)	25	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)
Swine	fixed cover (concrete, wood, tent)	25	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)

For solid manure storage systems, the MCFs are differentiated by livestock housing system (Table 14). Measurements in Austria have shown that CH₄ emissions from solid manure storage systems are lower than CH₄ emissions from liquid manure storage systems. Therefore, the MCF of 17% which is equal to the IPCC default value for liquid manure storage systems and applied for deep litter systems in Austria's National Inventory Report might overestimate CH₄ emissions (Anderl et al., 2023b). However, as no specific value is available for deep litter systems, we also apply the 17% in the DFEMS. This is in line with the MCF recommended by Arbeitsgruppe BEK (2021).

Table 14: Methane conversion factor (MCF) for solid manure storage systems by livestock category and type of livestock housing system (Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021; Haenel et al., 2020).

Livestock category	Housing system	MCF(S,T) (%)	Source
Cattle	deep litter/sloped floor	17	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Cattle ¹	tied systems/loose housing	2	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 119; Table 4.4)
Swine	deep litter	25	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)
Swine	other systems	3	Haenel et al. (2020, p. 200; Table 5.2)
Poultry		1.5	Arbeitsgruppe BEK (2021)

¹ not relevant for calves due to the ban of tied systems according to the animal protection law (*Tierschutzgesetz - TSchG*, n.d.)

For anaerobic digesters, the MCF of 2% is applied in Austria's National Inventory Report by referring to a study carried out in Germany (FNR, 2010, cited after Anderl et al., 2023b). For all other manure storage systems, we apply the MCFs for cool climate zones (Table 15), as provided by the IPCC (2006) and applied in Austria's National Inventory Report (Anderl et al., 2023b). Country-specific MCFs should be applied, if available. They are typically based on CH₄ emissions measured under field conditions.

Table 15: IPCC default MCF values for manure storage systems in cool climate zones for all livestock categories (IPCC, 2006).

Manure storage system	MCF(S,T) (%)
Manure deposited by grazing livestock on pasture, range, paddock	1
Solid manure storage systems	2
Anaerobic digester	2
Composting	0.5
Aerobic treatment	0

3.3.3. Nitrous oxide and ammonia emission calculation from manure management

N₂O as well as NH₃ and NO_x emissions from manure management result from the N excreted by the livestock categories and are produced directly and indirectly. Direct N₂O emissions occur during a combined process of nitrification and denitrification. Indirect N₂O emissions occur through volatilization and leaching. Equivalent to the previous emission sources, N₂O and NH₃ emissions from manure management should be calculated for each defined livestock sub-category.

The N excretion rates per defined livestock sub-category build the basis for calculating the N₂O emissions from manure management. First, the amount of N excreted per animal and year is calculated, which is then further used in the equations for calculating the direct and indirect N₂O emissions.

Step (i): N excretion rates per livestock sub-category

The farm-specific accounting of the average N excreted per year serves as an input for calculating the direct and indirect N₂O emissions from manure management. The total annual amount of N excreted by each livestock sub-category depends on how much N is consumed through the feed, and how much N is retained by the animal through e.g., body growth, milk production or gestation. Following a tier 2 approach for the farm-level calculation, the annual N excretion rate (N_{ex}(T); kg N animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) is calculated for each livestock sub-category T and is given by

$$N_{ex}(T) = (N_{intake}(T) - N_{retention}(T)) * 365 \quad (33)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.31A), where N_{intake}(T) is the amount of N intake in kg N per animal and day, and N_{retention}(T) is the amount of N that is retained by the animal in kg N per animal and day for growth, maintenance, and gestation. Multiplied with the number of days in a year, the annual amount of N excreted is calculated. For livestock sub-categories with multiple growth cycles or for livestock sub-categories with a lifetime shorter than one year, eq. (33) has to be adjusted concerning the multiplication of the specific days in the respective production or growth stage. The terms of eq. (33) can be further specified for the different livestock sub-categories.

N intake per livestock sub-category

For the **cattle livestock sub-categories**, the amount of N that is taken up by the animal (N_{intake}(T), kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is tied to the feed intake, i.e., the GE intake and the CP of a certain feed ration and is given by

$$N_{intake}(T) = \frac{GE(T)}{18.45} * \frac{CP}{6.25} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{cattle}\} \quad (34)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.32), where $GE(T)$ is given in MJ per animal and day (see eq. (15)), 18.45 is the conversion factor for the GE content to DMI in MJ per kg DM, and 6.25 is the conversion factor from CP to the dietary N content in kg CP per kg N.

For **swine and poultry livestock sub-categories**, the N intake through feed ($N_{\text{intake}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is calculated on the basis of the DMI. $N_{\text{intake}}(T)$ is given by

$$N_{\text{intake}}(T) = \text{DMI}(T) * \frac{\text{CP}}{6.25} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{swine, poultry}\} \quad (35)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.32A), where $\text{DMI}(T)$ is the dry matter intake during a specific growth stage in kg per animal and day, i.e., per defined livestock sub-category, and CP is the crude protein in the DM for the livestock sub-category T. The conversion factors are the same as those used for cattle. In the DFEMS as well as the application examples from Austria, we use the feed ration-specific CP value as queried per livestock sub-category for swine and poultry (see Section 3.1.3). This approach allows to further differentiate feeding phases if farmers specify different feeding phases when querying feed rations. Based on the number of feeding phases, it is also possible to compute an average CP content over all feeding phases if only one livestock sub-category is defined.

N retention per livestock sub-category

$N_{\text{retention}}(T)$ for cattle varies between lactating and non-lactating cattle livestock sub-categories due to different N requirements for milk production and growth.

For lactating cattle (i.e., dairy cows, suckling cows), the amount of N retained through the production of milk ($N_{\text{retention}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = \frac{\text{MilkProduction}(T) * \frac{\text{MilkProtein}(T)}{100}}{6.38} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{dairy cows, suckling cows}\} \quad (36)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.33), where $\text{MilkProduction}(T)$ is the milk production in kg per animal and day, $\text{MilkProtein}(T)$ is the protein content in the milk in percent and 6.38 is the conversion factor from milk protein to milk N in kg protein per kg N.

For non-lactating cattle sub-categories, the N retained in the body is through the weight gain ($N_{\text{retention}}(T)$; kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) and is given by

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = \frac{\text{WG}(T) * \left(\frac{268 - \frac{7.03 * \text{NE}_g(T)}{\text{WG}(T)}}{1000} \right)}{6.25} \quad (37)$$

if $T \in$ (young cattle up to 1 year, young cattle 1 – 2 years, breeding and fattening cattle)

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.33), where 268 and 7.03 are constants for the amount of protein in g protein per kg animal weight and in g protein per MJ and animal, respectively (NRC, 1996 cited after, IPCC, 2019), and 6.25 is the conversion from dietary protein to dietary N in kg protein per kg N.

$N_{\text{retention}}(T)$ for swine and poultry vary between the different livestock sub-categories due to different N requirements for breeding and growth.

The amount of N retained in **breeding sows** ($N_{\text{retention}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is the sum of N retained through the weight gain during gestation ($N_{\text{gain}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) and the N retained in the piglets ($N_{\text{weanedPiglets}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) weaned divided by the total number of days in the gestational and weaning periods; here we divide by 365 days to calculate the N retained in one day. It is given by

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = \frac{N_{\text{gain}}(T) + N_{\text{weanedPiglets}}(T)}{365} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\} \quad (38)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.33A).

$N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ in turn depends on the fertility rate ($\text{NumberAnnualGestations}(T)$) of the breeding sows, i.e., parturitions per year, the average litter size ($\text{LitterSize}(T)$, heads) and the birth weight of the piglets ($\text{pigletWt}_{\text{birth}}$, kg piglet⁻¹). $N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ (kg N animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{gain}}(T) = 0.025 * \text{NumberAnnualGestations}(T) * \left(\text{LitterSize}(T) * \frac{\text{pigletWt}_{\text{birth}}}{0.806} \right) \quad (39)$$

if $T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\}$

(IPCC, 2019, p. 10.86), where 0.025 is the fraction of N retained in the body in kg N per kg body weight. The latter part of the equation ($\text{LitterSize}(T) * \text{pigletWt}_{\text{birth}} * 0.806^{-1}$) is the total weight change of sows from parturition to parturition, i.e., per production cycle, with 0.806 being a constant to correct for the higher kg N per kg weight gain in piglets. Alternatively, to calculating the weight gain based on litter size and the birth weight of the piglets, this part of eq. (39) can be replaced by a value based on weight measurements of the breeding sow at the beginning and end of a gestation period.

The **N retention rates for piglets** ($N_{\text{weanedPiglets}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ year⁻¹) up to weaning is given by

$$N_{\text{weanedPiglets}}(T) = 0.025 * \text{NumberAnnualGestations}(T) * \text{LitterSize}(T) * \frac{\text{pigletWt}_{\text{weaned}} - \text{pigletWt}_{\text{birth}}}{0.98} \quad (40)$$

if $T \in \{\text{breeding sows}\}$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.33B), where $\text{pigletWt}_{\text{weaned}}$ is the live weight of piglets at weaning age in kg per piglet, 0.98 is the protein digestibility as fraction of the protein that is available for absorption after it is ingested, and 0.025 is again the N content of a piglets body (FAO, 2017, cited after, IPCC, 2019).

For **fattening pigs**, the N retained through growth ($N_{\text{retention}}(T)$, kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = \frac{(\text{BW}_{\text{final}}(T) - \text{BW}_{\text{initial}}(T)) * N_{\text{gain}}(T)}{\text{ProductionPeriod}(T)} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (41)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.33C), where $\text{BW}_{\text{final}}(T)$ is the live weight of the animal at the end of the livestock sub-category in kg, $\text{BW}_{\text{initial}}(T)$ is the live weight of the animal at the beginning of the livestock sub-category, and $N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ is a fraction of N retained at a given body weight. $N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ should be calculated for the final body weight of a livestock sub-category and is given by

$$N_{\text{gain}}(T) = -0.004 * \ln(\text{BW}_{\text{final}}(T)) + 0.0381 \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{fattening pigs}\} \quad (42)$$

(IPCC, 2019, p. 10.87; based on Shield et al, 1983, Poulsen & Kristensen, 1998, and FAO, 2017).

Like the feed requirement, the N retention rates for poultry differ depending on whether animals are used for egg or meat production and, therefore, between the livestock sub-categories laying hens and pullets or broilers.

For **laying hens**, $N_{\text{retention}}$ (kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = N_{\text{gain}}(T) * \text{WG}(T) + \left(\frac{N_{\text{egg}} * \text{EggProd}(T)}{1000} \right) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{laying hens}\} \quad (43)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.33D), where N_{gain} is the average N content in the live weight in kg N per animal, $WG(T)$ is the average daily weight gain for an animal in the sub-category T in kg per animal and day, N_{egg} is the average N content in eggs in kg N per kg egg mass, and EggProd is the egg mass production in g per animal and day. Again, farm-level data can be applied for $\text{EggProd}(T)$. For $N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ and N_{egg} , the default values 0.028 and 0.0185 are used in the DFEMS, respectively.

For **pullets or broilers**, $N_{\text{retention}}$ (kg N animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is derived by considering the farm-specific length of the production period and can be expressed as

$$N_{\text{retention}}(T) = \frac{(BW_{\text{final}}(T) - BW_{\text{initial}}(T)) * N_{\text{gain}}(T)}{\text{ProductionPeriod}(T)} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{pullets, broiler chicken}\} \quad (44)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.33E), where $\text{ProductionPeriod}(T)$ is the time period from chick to slaughter in days. In the DFEMS, we use the default value of 0.028 for $N_{\text{gain}}(T)$ (IPCC, 2019; based on Poulsen & Kristensen, 1998; FAO, 2017).

Step (ii): Direct nitrous oxide emissions from manure management

The tier 2 approach is applied in our DFEMS for calculating direct N₂O emissions from manure management at the farm level, i.e., the equations of the tier 1 approach are used, and the IPCC default values are replaced with farm-level data. For that, farm-level data is needed on (i) the type of manure management system (section 3.3.1), (ii) the amount of N excretion per livestock sub-category (derived in step (i)), and (iii) the distribution of manure if multiple manure storage systems are in place.

The total direct N₂O emissions from manure management ($N_2O_{D(\text{MM})}$; kg year⁻¹) of a farm are given by

$$N_2O_{D(\text{MM})} = \left[\sum_S \left[\sum_T \left((AAP(T) * N_{\text{ex}}(T)) * MS(S, T) \right) + N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T) \right] * EF_{N_2O, \text{MM}}(S, T) \right] * \frac{44}{28} \quad (45)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.25), where $AAP(T)$ is the annual average number of animals of the livestock sub-category T, or the $\text{livestock}_{\text{count}}(T)$ accordingly, multiplied by the N excretion rates ($N_{\text{ex}}(T)$) it results in the total amount of manure per livestock sub-category T. $MS(S, T)$ is the fraction of the total annual N excretion per livestock sub-category T managed in manure management system S, $N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T)$ is the amount of N that is added from the anaerobic digestion system in kg N per year, $EF_{N_2O, \text{MM}}(S, T)$ is the emission factor for direct N₂O emissions from manure management system S in kg N₂O-N per kg N. The conversion from kg N₂O-N to kg N₂O is done by applying the conversion factor $44 * 28^{-1}$.

For an accurate non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting at the farm level we apply the N₂O emission factors provided by the Arbeitsgruppe BEK (2021) from the KTBL. These N₂O emission factors are differentiated by livestock (sub-) category, type of manure, and type of manure storage cover (Table 16).

Table 16: N₂O emission factors for direct N₂O emissions from manure storage by livestock (sub-) category, type of manure, and manure storage cover (adopted from Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021).

Livestock (sub-) category	Manure storage system	Manure storage cover	$EF_{N_2O, \text{MM}}(S, T)$ (kg N ₂ O-N/(kg N_{ex} + N_{Straw}))
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	not covered	0.01
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	fixed cover	0.005
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	synthetic cover (foil)	0
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.005
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	straw cover	0.005
Cattle	Liquid/slurry	below slatted floor	0.002
Cattle	Solid – other systems*		0.005
Cattle	Solid – deep litter*		0.01

Cattle	Anaerobic digesters	open storage with natural crust	0.005
Cattle	Anaerobic digesters	gas-tight storage	0
Swine	Solid – deep litter*		0.01
Swine	Solid – other systems*		0.005
Swine	Liquid/slurry	fixed cover	0.005
Swine	Liquid/slurry	synthetic cover (foil)	0
Swine	Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.005
Swine	Liquid/slurry	straw cover	0.005
Swine	Liquid/slurry	without a natural straw cover	0
Swine	Liquid/slurry	below slatted floor	0.002
Swine	Liquid/slurry	below slatted floor	0.002
Swine	Anaerobic digesters	open storage with natural crust	0.005
Swine	Anaerobic digesters	gas-tight storage	0
Laying hens	Solid*		0.001
Broiler	Solid*		0.001
Poultry	Anaerobic digesters	open storage with natural crust	0.005
Poultry	Anaerobic digesters	gas-tight storage	0

* N₂O emissions from manure in stable and storage

If detailed farm-level data on the type of manure storage system and cover is not available, the following standard N₂O emission factors for different manure storage systems can be used. These values are applicable for all livestock sub-categories, unless otherwise specified (IPCC, 2019).

Table 17: Default emission factors for direct N₂O emissions by manure management systems (IPCC, 2019, p. 10.91)

Manure storage system	Manure storage cover and treatment	EF _{N₂O,MM(S,T)} (kg N ₂ O-N/kg N _{ex})
Daily spread		0
Liquid/slurry	uncovered	0
Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.005
Liquid/slurry	covered	0.005
Solid	uncovered	0.01
Solid	covered/compacted	0.01
Solid	bulking agent addition	0.005
Solid	additives	0.005
Anaerobic digesters		0
Deep bedding – swine and cattle	no mixing	0.01
	active mixing	0.07
Deep bedding – poultry	with and without litter	0.001
Composting – in-vessel		0.006
Composting – static pile		0.006
Composting – intensive windrow		0.1
Composting – passive windrow		0.01
Aerobic treatment	natural aeration system	0.01
	forced aeration system	0.005

* Detailed definitions of the different manure management systems are available in IPCC (2019; tab. 10.21).

Farms that add N from anaerobic digesters, i.e., agricultural biogas plants, to their manure storage system can apply the following (Table 18) default values for the N content (N_{ContentBiogas(T)}) in kg N per 1,000 kg fresh matter (FM) digestives depending on the livestock category.

Table 18: Default values of the N content of digestates from anaerobic digesters for different livestock categories (Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021)

Livestock category	Manure storage system	N content (kg N/1,000 kg FM)
Cattle	Liquid digestate from anaerobic digesters	4.4
Cattle	Solid digestate from anaerobic digesters	5.0
Swine	Liquid digestate from anaerobic digesters	5.5
Poultry	Solid digestate from anaerobic digesters	22.2

The amount of N that is added from the anaerobic digestion system ($N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T)$; kg N year⁻¹) can be calculated with

$$N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T) = N_{\text{ContentBiogas}}(T) * FM_{\text{Digestate}}(T) \quad (46)$$

(own calculation), where $N_{\text{ContentBiogas}}(T)$ is the amount of N in kg per 1,000 kg FM of a specific livestock category T and $FM_{\text{Digestate}}(T)$ is the fresh matter of digestates from anaerobic digesters in kg.

Step (iii): Indirect nitrous oxide emissions from manure management in forms of NH₃ and NO_x

The storage of manure also results in ammonia (NH₃) and nitric oxides (NO_x) emissions. These emissions can be interpreted as N losses that begin at the point of livestock manure excretion and continue to arise during manure storage and management. For calculating the indirect N₂O emissions from manure management at the farm level, we again follow the tier 2 approach. Similar to the approach applied for direct N₂O emissions from manure management, indirect N₂O emissions from manure management are calculated by applying the equations of the tier 1 approach to farm-level input data.

N losses through volatilization from manure management

First, the N losses due to volatilization, i.e., the emission of N to the atmosphere as NH₃ and NO_x, and leaching from manure management are derived. Volatilization of NH₃ and NO_x ($N_{\text{volatilisation(MM)}}$; kg N year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{volatilisation(MM)}} = \sum_S \left[\sum_T \left[\left((AAP(T) * N_{\text{ex}}(T)) * MS(S, T) \right) + N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T) \right] * \text{FRAC}_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T) \right] \quad (47)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.26), where $\text{FRAC}_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T)$ is the fraction of managed manure N for the livestock sub-category T that volatilizes as NH₃ and NO_x in the manure management system S. The default values for the N loss fractions due to volatilization ($\text{FRAC}_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T)$) of NH₃ and NO_x differ between manure storage system and cover as well as livestock sub-categories. Table 20 summarizes the default values applied in the DFEMS.

Second, after calculating N losses due to volatilization, the indirect N₂O emissions due to volatilization ($N_{2O_{G(MM)}}$; kg year⁻¹) are given by

$$N_{2O_{G(MM)}} = (N_{\text{volatilisation(MM)}} * EF_{N_{2O(MM),ATD}}) * \frac{44}{28} \quad (48)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.28), where $EF_{N_{2O(MM),ATD}}$ is the emission factor for N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N on soils and water surfaces in kg N₂O-N per kg NH₃-N + NO_x-N volatilized (Table 19).

N losses through leaching and run-off from manure management

Similarly, the indirect N₂O emissions from leaching and run-off from manure management ($N_{\text{leaching(MM)}}$; in kg N year⁻¹) can be calculated in two steps.

First, the N losses due to leaching from manure management are derived. N leached ($N_{\text{leaching(MM)}}$; kg N year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{\text{leaching(MM)}} = \sum_S \left[\sum_T \left[\left((AAP(T) * Nex(T)) * MS(S, T) \right) + N_{\text{biogas}}(S, T) \right) * FRAC_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T) \right] \right] \quad (49)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.27), where $FRAC_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T)$ is the fraction of managed manure N for the livestock sub-category T that is leached from the manure management systems S. The default values for the N loss fraction due to leaching ($FRAC_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T)$) in form of NH_3 and NO_x differ between manure storage system and cover as well as livestock sub-categories (Table 20).

Second, the indirect N_2O emissions due to leaching ($N_2O_{L(MM)}$; $kg N_2O \text{ year}^{-1}$) from manure management can be expressed as

$$N_2O_{L(MM)} = (N_{\text{leaching(MM)}} * EF_{N_2O(MM),L}) * \frac{44}{28} \quad (50)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 10.29), where $EF_{N_2O(MM),L}$ is the emission factor for N_2O emissions from leaching and runoff in $kg N_2O-N$ per $kg N$ leached and runoff (Table 19).

Box 13: Indirect N_2O emissions through leaching and run-off from manure storage systems in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

Austrian laws concerning the construction of manure storage systems require farmers to build watertight animal housings and manure storage systems. In order for farmers to receive funding and subsidies, this water tightness has to be officially certified (ÖKL-Merkblatt 2011 cited after Anderl et al., 2023b). Given the legal framework in Austria, leaching and run-off from manure management systems is considered as non-existent, i.e., no indirect N_2O emissions from leaching and run-off from manure storage systems are calculated at the farm level.

Table 19 outlines the two emission factors ($EF_{N_2O(MM),ATD}$ and $EF_{N_2O(MM),L}$) used for the calculation of indirect N_2O emissions from manure management.

Table 19: Default emission factors for volatilization and leaching/runoff from manure management (IPCC, 2019, p. 11.26)

Emission factor	Aggregated	Disaggregated	Default value
$EF_{N_2O(MM),ATD}$; N volatilization	0.01	Wet climate	0.014
		Dry climate	0.005
$EF_{N_2O(MM),L}$; N leaching/runoff	0.011	-	-

Table 20 summarizes the default values for $FRAC_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T)$ and $FRAC_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T)$ differentiated by manure management system, cover and livestock () category. It should be noted that N losses from manure below a slatted floor in enclosed livestock confinement facilities, i.e., pit storage below animal confinements, is not considered in the DFEMS.

Table 20: Default values for N loss fractions in form of NH_3 and NO_x (adapted from IPCC, 2019, tab. 10.22)

Livestock (sub-) category	Manure management system	Manure storage cover and treatment	$FRAC_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T)$	$FRAC_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T)$
Dairy cattle	Liquid/slurry	not covered	0.48	0.00
Dairy cattle	Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.30	0.00
Dairy cattle	Liquid/slurry	with cover (straw, synthetic, fixed)	0.10	0.00
Dairy cattle	Solid	not covered	0.30	0.02
Dairy cattle	Solid	covered/compacted	0.15	0.00

Dairy cattle	Solid	bulking agent addition	0.38	0.02
Dairy cattle	Solid	additives	0.11	0.02
Dairy cattle	Anaerobic digesters		0.05 – 0.50	0.00
Dairy cattle	Solid	deep bedding	0.25	0.035
Other cattle	Liquid/slurry	not covered	0.48	0.00
Other cattle	Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.30	0.00
Other cattle	Liquid/slurry	with cover (straw, synthetic, fixed)	0.10	0.00
Other cattle	Solid	uncovered	0.45	0.02
Other cattle	Solid	covered/compacted	0.22	0.00
Other cattle	Solid	bulking agent addition	0.58	0.02
Other cattle	Solid	additives	0.17	0.02
Other cattle	Anaerobic digesters		0.05 – 0.50	0.00
Other cattle	Solid	deep bedding	0.25	0.035
Swine	Liquid/slurry	not covered	0.48	0.00
Swine	Liquid/slurry	natural crust	0.30	0.00
Swine	Liquid/slurry	with cover (straw, synthetic, fixed)	0.10	0.00
Swine	Solid	uncovered	0.45	0.02
Swine	Solid	covered/compacted	0.22	0.00
Swine	Solid	bulking agent addition	0.58	0.02
Swine	Solid	additives	0.17	0.02
Swine	Anaerobic digesters		0.05 – 0.50	0.00
Swine	Solid	deep bedding	0.40	0.035
Poultry	Liquid/slurry	not covered	0.40	0.00
Poultry	Liquid/slurry	with cover (straw, synthetic, fixed)	0.08	0.00
Poultry	Solid	deep litter systems*	0.28	0.00
Poultry	Solid	uncovered	0.40	0.02
Poultry	Solid	covered/compacted	0.20	0.00
Poultry	Solid	bulking agent addition	0.54	0.02
Poultry	Solid	additives	0.16	0.02
Poultry	Anaerobic digesters		0.05 – 0.50	0.00

Box 14: Austrian-specific values for the N loss fractions due to volatilization ($FRAC_{gasMM}(S, T)$) in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the Austrian Inventory Report, the value applied for $FRAC_{gasMM}(S, T)$ in N losses per N excreted is 0.16, i.e., 16 % of the N excretion is lost as NH_3 and NO_x .

Austrian-specific values for the N losses through volatilization in forms of NH_3 and NO_x exist. These fractions are calculated with the Austrian N-flow model and include NH_3 losses from housing and manure storage, and NO_x losses from manure management. The N-flow model, i.e., the mass-flow approach, is based on the total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN; Anderl et al., 2023a); TAN refers to the nitrogen in ammoniacal form, i.e., $NH_3 + NH_4^+$ (ammonium) in g N per m^3 livestock manure (Sommer et al., 2022). As a first step, the TAN content in the excreted livestock manure has to be known. For calculating the amount of N excreted by cattle, swine, and poultry, see step (i) of section 3.3.3. The EMEP/EEA Guidebook (European Environment Agency, 2023) provides these values, as well as default tier 2 NH_3 -N emission factors for the calculation of the NH_3 -N emissions from manure management (European Environment Agency, 2023). Table 21 summarizes default values for the different livestock sub-categories and types of manure.

Table 21: Proportion of TAN and NH_3 -N emission factors (EF) (European Environment Agency, 2023; Tab 3-9)

Livestock sub-category	TAN content	Manure type	NH_3 -N EF for housing	NH_3 -N EF for manure storage (kg NH_3 -N (kg TAN) ⁻¹)	NH_3 -N EF for grazing
Dairy cows	0.6	Slurry	0.24	0.25	0.14
Dairy cows	0.6	Solid	0.08	0.32	0.14
Dairy cows, tied housing	0.6	Slurry	0.09	0.25	0.14
Dairy cows, tied housing	0.6	Solid	0.09	0.32	0.14
Non-dairy cattle	0.6	Slurry	0.24	0.25	0.14
Non-dairy cattle	0.6	Solid	0.08	0.32	0.14
Fattening pigs	0.7	Slurry	0.27	0.11	-
Fattening pigs	0.7	Solid	0.23	0.29	-
Sows	0.7	Slurry	0.35	0.11	-
Sows	0.7	Solid	0.24	0.29	-
Sows	0.7	Outdoors in small huts for shelter	-	-	0.31
Piglets < 8 kg	0.7	Slurry	0.35	0.11	-
Piglets < 8 kg	0.7	Solid	0.24	0.29	-
Piglets 30-35 kg	0.7	Outdoors in small huts for shelter	-	-	0.31
Laying hens	0.7	Solid	0.20	0.08	-
Laying hens	0.7	Slurry	0.41	0.14	-
Broiler chickens	0.7	Solid	0.21	0.30	-

The Austrian Informative Inventory Report provides national values for the TAN content of cattle and swine manure (Schechtner 1991 and BMLFUW, 2017 cited after Anderl et al., 2023a). Table 22 presents these values for solid and liquid manure in kg NH_3 per kg N excreted.

Table 22: TAN content of Austrian cattle and swine manure (Schechtner 1991 and BMLFUW, 2017 cited after Anderl et al., 2023a)

Livestock category	Manure management system	NH ₃ -N EF (kg NH ₃ -N (kg TAN) ⁻¹)
Cattle	Liquid/ slurry manure storage system	0.15
Cattle	Solid manure storage system	0.30
Swine	Liquid/ slurry manure storage system	0.12
Swine	Solid manure storage system	0.30

For calculating the NH₃ emissions of poultry, the Austrian GHG inventory makes use of the tier 2 approach provided by the EMEP/EEA Guidebook 2019 (European Environment Agency, 2019). This approach follows a mass flow approach. For cattle and swine, we use the Austrian specific N-flow approach due to the availability of detailed farm-level data on livestock characteristics and manure management.

Calculation of NH₃ emissions for cattle and swine

The NH₃ emissions from cattle and swine can be calculated with

$$NH_3(T) = NH_{3(\text{housing})} + NH_{3(\text{storage})} \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{cattle, swine}\} \quad (51)$$

(Anderl et al., 2023a), where the NH₃ emissions are the sum of the NH₃-N emissions from housing (NH_{3(housing)} in kg NH₃-N) and from manure storage (NH_{3(storage)} in kg NH₃-N).

The NH₃ emission factors for the losses related to the livestock housing differentiate between livestock (sub-) category, housing system, and manure storage system. Table 23 provides NH₃ emission factors for the livestock categories cattle and swine.

Table 23: Emission factors for NH₃ emissions from housing of cattle and swine (Eidgenössische Forschungsanstalt, 1997 and Döhler et al., 2002 cited after Anderl et al., 2023a)

Livestock (sub-) category	Housing system	Manure storage system	NH ₃ -N EF (kg NH ₃ -N (kg N excreted) ⁻¹)
Cattle	Grazing	Manure deposited on grazing area	0.050
Cattle	Tied systems	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	0.040
Cattle	Tied systems	Solid manure storage system	0.039
Cattle	Loose housing	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	0.118
Cattle	Loose housing	Solid manure storage system	0.118
Fattening pigs	all	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	0.150
Fattening pigs	all	Solid manure storage system	15 % of total N + 30 % of the remaining TAN

The basis for calculating the NH₃ emissions is the amount of N left in the livestock manure when entering the manure storage system. Thereof, in order to derive the NH₃ emissions from manure storage, the N excreted during grazing and the NH₃-N losses from housing are subtracted from the total N excretion. The amount of N entering the manure storage system depends on the fraction of the year that livestock spend in the housing system or on grazing. Table 24 summarizes the NH₃ emission factors for manure storage which differentiate between livestock categories and the type of manure storage system.

Table 24: Emission factors for NH₃ emissions from livestock manure storage for cattle and swine (Eidgenössische Forschungsanstalt, 1997 cited after Anderl et al., 2023a)

Livestock category	Manure management system	NH ₃ -N EF (kg NH ₃ -N (kg TAN) ⁻¹)
Cattle	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	0.15
Cattle	Solid manure storage system	0.30
Swine	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	0.12
Swine	Solid manure storage system	0.30

Calculation of NH₃ emissions for poultry

For poultry livestock categories, we follow the EMEP/EEA tier 2 approach which has also been applied in the national emission inventory report (Anderl et al., 2023b; European Environment Agency, 2019). We use the default values of the TAN content of poultry manure provided by the EMEP/EEA Guidebook 2019 (see Table 25).

Table 25: Default NH₃-N EF and TAN content (European Environment Agency, 2019)

Livestock sub-category	TAN content	Manure type	NH ₃ -N EF for housing; EF _{housing(NH₃)(T)} (kg NH ₃ -N (kg TAN) ⁻¹)	NH ₃ -N EF for manure storage (kg NH ₃ -N (kg TAN) ⁻¹)
Laying hens	0.7	Solid	0.20	0.08
Laying hens	0.7	Slurry	0.41	0.14
Broiler chickens	0.7	Solid	0.21	0.30

The NH₃-N emission from housing can be calculated by

$$NH_3(T) = Nex(S) * TAN_{content}(T) * EF_{housing(NH_3)}(T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{poultry}\} \quad (52)$$

(Anderl et al., 2023a), where $Nex(S)$ is the amount of N excreted per manure management system S in kg per year (see section 3.3.3 for calculation), $TAN_{content}(T)$ is the livestock sub-category related TAN content of poultry manure, and $EF_{housing(NH_3)}(T)$ is the emission factor for the N losses from housing.

The total amount of N excreted per manure management system S can be calculated based on the annual N excreted per animal with

$$Nex(S) = \sum_T AAP(T) * Nex(T) * MS(S, T) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{poultry}\} \quad (53)$$

(Anderl et al., 2023a), where $AAP(T)$ is the average annual population of the poultry livestock sub-category (see eq. (1)), $Nex(T)$ is the annual N excreted in kg N by the livestock sub-category T and $MS(S, T)$ is the fraction of manure that is collected and stored in the manure management system S .

Assuming that poultry manure is mostly stored as solid manure, the portion of the TAN that become immobilized in the organic matter of the litter, i.e., straw, is taken into account. The amount that is converted into organic forms reduces the amount of the TAN available to be volatilized as NH₃ (European Environment Agency, 2019). The NH₃-N emission from poultry manure storage can be calculated by

$$NH_3(T) = (Nex(S) * TAN_{content}(T)) - (EF_{housing(NH_3)}(T) + (Straw_{FM}(T) * OM_{immobil})) \quad \text{if } T \in \{\text{poultry}\} \quad (54)$$

(European Environment Agency, 2019), where $Straw_{FM}(T)$ is the amount of bedding in kg fresh weight per year (see Table 28 for Austrian-specific values), and $OM_{immobil}$ is the fraction TAN that is immobilised in organic matter when manure is managed as a litter-based solid and the litter is straw. The EEA provides a default value for of 0.0067 kg per kg straw used (Webb and Misselbrook, 2004, cited after (European Environment Agency, 2019)).

4. Non-CO₂ GHG emissions from managed agricultural soils

N₂O naturally forms in the soil through nitrification and denitrification processes. Nitrification is the aerobic process where ammonium (NH₄⁺) is oxidized to nitrate (NO₃⁻) by microbes, while denitrification is the anaerobic process where NO₃⁻ is reduced to nitrogen gas (N₂). N₂O is a gaseous intermediate in the denitrification process and is released during nitrification, entering the soil and eventually the atmosphere. The availability of inorganic N in the soil plays a key role in these processes. The N₂O emissions resulting from N inputs or N mineralization occur through a direct and indirect pathway:

- Direct N₂O emissions occur directly from the soils to which N is added.
- Indirect N₂O emissions occur through (i) volatilization of NH₃ and NO_x, which are then redeposited including their products NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ into soils and water bodies and (ii) leaching and runoff of N in the form of NO₃⁻.

For estimating N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils, we follow the tier 2 approach provided by the IPCC (2019) by using a common set of activity data, i.e., N inputs. The IPCC methodology considers six different N inputs for calculating N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils:

- (1) N from the application of organic fertilizer (F_{ON}; e.g., livestock manure),
- (2) N from the application of synthetic fertilizer (F_{SN}),
- (3) N from urine and dung deposited on pasture, range, and paddock by grazing livestock (F_{PRP}),
- (4) N in crop residues, including N-fixing crops and forages during pasture renewal (F_{CR}),
- (5) N mineralization resulting from the loss of soil organic matter through land use or management changes (F_{SOM}), and
- (6) N from the management of organic soils (F_{OS}).

Within the scope of the present protocol and the DFEMS, the focus lies on N inputs (1) to (4). The N sources (5) and (6) are not considered in the protocol and DFEMS due to the lack of data at the farm level. The equations provided by the IPCC (2019) are adapted according to the focus of the DFEMS, i.e., terms not considered are omitted.

This section presents the data requirements, methods, and equations for deriving direct and indirect N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils, including cropland and grassland. The IPCC (2019) provides generic equations that can be applied for estimating N₂O emissions within specific land use categories.

In order to derive the non-CO₂ GHG emissions from managed agricultural soils as accurately as possible, the presented approach must be applied for each cultivated crop type and type of grassland, respectively. This requires farm-level data on farming activities and farm management practices at a disaggregated level, i.e., information on N use activities (such as synthetic fertilizer application) has to be available for a specific crop. In case different management intensities are applied to several fields of the same crop, the presented approach should be applied at the field-level. The results for all crops and fields are summed up to obtain non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level.

4.1. Soil management related farm-level input data

The indirect and direct N₂O emissions are calculated separately using a common set of activity data. For deriving non-CO₂ GHG emissions from managed agricultural soils in the DFEMS, we query detailed information on land use and land management from all farms that cultivate land – this includes both cropland and grassland as well as farms with livestock grazing on pastures. In addition to the information queried on livestock grazing (section 3.1.2), the following data on land use and land management is collected in the DFEMS:

- The **crop type** and **field size** (ha) of cropland and grassland (including pastures) are important information for the N balance.
- Share of under sowing or intercropping and its crop type.

- The **dry matter yield** (t DM ha⁻¹ or t DM field⁻¹) is needed per crop, or if variable due to, e.g., different soil qualities, it should be available per field. It is one of the key factors influencing a crops nutrient demand.

For farmers applying livestock manure to their fields, the following information must be available for each crop or field:

- The **type of manure applied to the soil** for livestock farms, as well as for crop farms buying-in manure for application to the soil. Based on the type of manure storage system, the type of manure applied to soils has to be differentiated in solid, liquid and slurry manure (for details see section 3.3.1). As the N content in the manure varies between livestock sub-categories, this differentiation should also be made when deriving non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agricultural soils. Default values for the N content are available from the Richtlinien für die sachgerechte Düngung im Ackerbau und Grünland (Austrian fertilizer recommendations for crop farming and grassland; BMLRT, 2022).
- The **amount of manure applied to the soil** (m³ ha⁻¹) must be specified for each application time. From this information, the proportions of N, phosphorus (P) and potassium (K; all in kg (m³)⁻¹) can be derived.
- **Manure application method**, differentiating between
 - Broadcasting
 - Trailing hose
 - Trailing shoe
 - Injection technique
 - Slurry cultivator
 - Slot injection
- **Incorporation time of manure**, differentiating between
 - Not incorporated
 - Directly
 - ≤ 1 hour
 - 1 to ≤ 4 hours
 - 4 to ≤ 12 hours
 - 12 to ≤ 24 hours
 - 24 to ≤ 48 hours
- For livestock farms, the **amount of bedding** (kg animal⁻¹ day⁻¹) is relevant for deriving the manure-N available for application to the soils and is queried in the DFEMS. This information can only be considered for livestock farms, but it is not available for crop farms that purchase manure.

For farmers applying synthetic fertilizer to their soils, the following information is needed at the field level:

- The **fertilizer type** is important as it can be linked to detailed information on the nutrient content of different fertilizers and, therefore, provides information on the N, P, and K content of the applied fertilizer.
- The **amount of synthetic fertilizer applied** (kg ha⁻¹ or kg field⁻¹) to agricultural soils is needed for each application time. For further use of total synthetic fertilizer application per crop in the IPCC equations, the amount per ha can be multiplied by the field size of a specific crop and summed over all synthetic fertilizer applications per year.
- **Liming** (kg CaO ha⁻¹)
- Information on **plant residues**, i.e., whether plant residues are left on fields and for which crop type.
- The **soil pH** is relevant since the application of different fertilizer types cause different amounts of emissions whether the soil is calcareous. i.e., a pH of >7, or normal, i.e., a pH <7.

Box 15: Fertilizer types considered in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the data query tool used to collect data for the DFEMS, all fertilizers approved for application in Austria and the respective nutrient contents, i.e., N, P, and K, are stored in a database and can be selected by farmers for the application to agricultural soils. In combination with the applied amount of fertilizer (in kg ha⁻¹ or kg field⁻¹, respectively) this provides the necessary information for deriving non-CO₂ GHG emissions synthetic fertilizer applications to agricultural soils.

4.2. Nitrous oxide emission calculation from managed agricultural soils

4.2.1. Step (i): Manure-N available for application to agricultural soils

According to the IPCC (2006), the total N₂O emissions from applying manure to agricultural soils consist of the partial contribution of various livestock sub-categories. Therefore, the following equations are applied for every defined livestock sub-category, which is in accordance with the non-CO₂ GHG emissions from enteric fermentation and manure management (section 3).

The N from manure that is available for application to soils ($N_{MM_{Avl}}(S, T)$; kg N year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_{MM_{Avl}}(S, T) = \sum_S \left[\sum_T [(AAP(T) * Nex(T) * MS(S, T) + N_{biogas}(S, T)) * (1 - FRAC_{lossMM}(S, T))] + (AAP(T) * MS(S, T) * N_{bedding}(S, T)) \right] \quad (55)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.34), where $N_{biogas}(S, T)$ is the amount of N from co-digestates added to biogas plants in kg per year, $FRAC_{lossMM}(S, T)$ is the total fraction of managed manure N for livestock sub-category T that is lost in the manure management system S, and $N_{bedding}(S, T)$ is the amount of N from bedding added to the manure in kg per animal and year.

In order to derive the amount of N from bedding, the EMEP/EEA-Guidebook (European Environment Agency, 2019) provides information on the annual straw use in litter-based manure management systems. Table 26 provides the data for the livestock categories cattle and swine.

Table 26: Default values for the annual straw use (kg head⁻¹ year⁻¹) (adapted from European Environment Agency, 2019)

Livestock (sub-)category	Straw use (kg head ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Dairy cattle	1,500
Non-dairy cattle	500
Fattening pigs	200
Breeding sows incl. litter	600

Box 16: Values for straw use considered in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

For the Austrian case study at hand, expert judgement is available for the straw use for the livestock sub-categories dairy cattle, suckling cows and young cattle as well as for poultry (see Table 27 and Table 28). For the other cattle sub-categories and swine, we apply the values provided by the EMEP/EEA-Guidebook in Table 26 (European Environment Agency, 2019). For the time animals are kept on pastures, no straw is used.

Table 27: Straw use for cattle based on the housing system and manure storage system (Anderl et al., 2023a).

Livestock sub-category	Housing system	Manure storage system	Straw use (kg head ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Dairy cattle and suckling cows	Tied housing	Solid manure storage system	547.5
Dairy cattle and suckling cows	Tied housing	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	73.0
Dairy cattle and suckling cows	Loose housing	Solid manure storage system	1,460.0
Dairy cattle and suckling cows	Loose housing	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	182.5
Young cattle	Tied housing	Solid manure storage system	438.0
Young cattle	Tied housing	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	73.0
Young cattle	Loose housing	Solid manure storage system	912.5
Young cattle	Loose housing	Liquid/slurry manure storage system	109.5

The straw use for poultry is given in Table 28.

Table 28: Straw use for poultry (Anderl et al., 2023a).

Livestock sub-category	Manure storage system	Straw use (kg head ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Laying hens	Solid manure storage system	0.5
Broilers	Solid manure storage system	1.4

As we do not differentiate between different types of beddings, i.e., different N contents of straw from different cereals, we follow the Austrian National Inventory Report and apply an N content of 0.004 kg N per kg straw (Anderl et al., 2023a).

Eq. (55) can be further specified, given the following equations.

FRAC_{lossMM}(S, T) is the sum of N losses through emissions from volatilization (FRAC_{gasMM}(S, T)), leaching or runoff (FRAC_{leachMM}(S, T); see Table 20), as N₂ FRAC_{N₂MM}(S, T)), and direct N₂O emissions from manure storage system S (EF_{N₂O,MM}(S, T); see Table 16), and expressed as

$$\text{FRAC}_{\text{lossMM}}(S, T) = \text{FRAC}_{\text{gasMM}}(S, T) + \text{FRAC}_{\text{leachMM}}(S, T) + \text{FRAC}_{\text{N}_2\text{MM}}(S, T) \quad (56)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.34A). Thereof, the fraction of N₂ emissions is calculated as

$$\text{FRAC}_{\text{N}_2\text{MM}}(S, T) = R_{\text{N}_2(\text{N}_2\text{O})} * \text{EF}_{\text{N}_2\text{O,MM}}(S, T) \quad (57)$$

(IPCC, 2019 eq. 10.34B), where $R_{N_2(N_2O)}$ is the ratio of $N_2:N_2O$ emissions. In the DFEMS we apply the IPCC default value of 3 kg N_2-N per kg N_2O-N (IPCC, 2019).

4.2.2. Step (ii): Direct nitrous oxide emissions from managed agricultural soils

Based on the IPCC methodology, the direct N_2O emissions from managed soils ($N_2O_{D(Soils)}$, kg N_2O year⁻¹) are defined as the sum of N inputs to soils and the N inputs on grazed soils are given by

$$N_2O_{D(Soils)} = (N_2O - N_{Ninputs} + N_2O - N_{PRP}) * \frac{44}{28} \quad (58)$$

(adapted from IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.1), where $N_2O - N_{Ninputs}$ are the annual direct N_2O-N emissions from N inputs to agricultural soils in kg N_2O-N per year, and $N_2O - N_{PRP}$ are the annual direct N_2O-N emissions from urine and dung inputs to grazed soils in kg N_2O-N per year. PRP stands for pasture, range and paddock. N_2O-N emissions are converted to N_2O emissions by multiplying the calculated N_2O-N emissions by the conversion factor $44 * 28^{-1}$ (IPCC, 2019).

The availability of farm-level data on, e.g., synthetic fertilizer inputs, allows to further disaggregate eq. (58) as follows:

Direct N_2O-N emissions from N inputs to the soil

The direct N_2O-N emissions from N inputs ($N_2O - N_{Ninputs}$; kg N_2O-N year⁻¹) can be further disaggregated and expressed as

$$N_2O - N_{Ninputs} = (F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{CR}) * EF_{N_2O,Ninputs} \quad (59)$$

(adapted from IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.1), where F_{SN} is the amount of N from synthetic fertilizer in kg N per year applied. F_{ON} is the N from organic fertilizers (e.g., animal manure, compost, sewage sludge, other organic N additions) in kg N per year, as derived in section 4.2. F_{CR} is the amount of N in crop residues returned to soils in kg N per year, and $EF_{N_2O,Ninputs}$ is the emission factor for N_2O emissions from N inputs in kg N_2O-N per kg N input. The detailed information on the type and amount of synthetic fertilizer applied to cropland and grassland allows to use a fertilizer-specific value for F_{SN} .

The **total amount of organic N fertilizer** (F_{ON} ; kg N year⁻¹) applied to soils other than by grazing animals is given by

$$F_{ON} = F_{AM} + F_{SEW} + F_{COMP} + F_{OOA} \quad (60)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.3), where F_{AM} is the amount of N in livestock manure applied to soils in kg N per year, F_{SEW} is the amount of N in total sewage that is applied to soils in kg per year, F_{COMP} is the amount of total compost N applied to soils in kg N per year, and F_{OOA} is the amount of other organic amendments used as fertilizer, such as brewery waste, in kg N per year. In the DFEMS, we apply farm-level data on the total annual manure application to soils and its N-content, as derived in section 4.2. Therefore, the F_{AM} is determined by reducing the total available N in manure in kg N per year ($N_{MMAVl}(S, T)$, eq. (55)) by the fraction of managed manure used for feed ($FRAC_{feed}$), burnt for fuel ($FRAC_{fuel}$), or used for construction ($FRAC_{constr}$). Therefore, F_{AM} (kg N year⁻¹) is given by

$$F_{AM} = N_{MMAVl}(S, T) * [1 - (FRAC_{feed} + FRAC_{fuel} + FRAC_{constr})] \quad (61)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.4).

Box 17: Usage of livestock manure in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In the DFEMS we assume that livestock manure is only used for application to soils, therefore, the value of $N_{MMAvl}(S, T)$ (see eq. (55)) can be used as F_{AM} without adjustments.

The amount of N in crop residues returned to soils (F_{CR} ; kg N year⁻¹) includes above- and below-ground biomass and N-fixing crops. The N from crop residues is calculated from farm-specific crop yields, crop-specific default factors for above- and below-ground residue:yield ratios and the N content in residues. Different crop types vary in residue:yield ratios (i.e., the amount of crop residues left in relation to the crop yield), renewal time and N contents. That is why the N from residues is calculated separately for the major crop types: (1) non-fixing grain crops (e.g., wheat, maize, barley), (2) N-fixing grains and pulses (e.g., lentils, soybean), (3) root and tuber crops (e.g., potato), (4) N-fixing forage crops (e.g., clover), (5) other forages including perennial grasses and grass/clover pastures. The N values from all crop types can then be summed up.

F_{CR} is given by

$$F_{CR} = \sum_C \left[\left[AGR(C) * N_{AG}(C) * (1 - FRAC_{remove}(C) - (FRAC_{burnt}(C) * Cf)) \right] + [BGR(C) * N_{BG}(C)] \right] \quad (62)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.6), where $AGR(C)$ is the total amount of above-ground residues for crop C in kg DM per year, $N_{AG}(C)$ is the N content of above-ground residues for crop C in kg N per kg DM, $FRAC_{remove}(C)$ is the fraction of above-ground residues of crop C removed annually for purposes such as bedding, $FRAC_{burnt}(C)$ is the fraction of annual harvested area of crop C that is burnt, Cf is the combustion factor, $BGR(C)$ is the total amount of below-ground residues for crop C in kg DM per year, and $N_{BG}(C)$ is the N content of below-ground residues for crop C in kg N per kg DM.

Box 18: Burning of harvest in the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In Austria, the burning of harvested areas is legally not allowed and negligible. Therefore, the fraction of the annual harvested area of crop C that is burnt, i.e., $FRAC_{burnt}(C)$, and the respective combustion factor Cf are assumed to be 0 in the application examples of the DFEMS.

Above-ground residues ($AGR(C)$, kg DM year⁻¹) is further given by

$$AGR(C) = AG_{DM}(C) * area(C) \quad (63)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.6), where $AG_{DM}(C)$ is the above-ground residue DM for crop C in kg DM per ha and $area(C)$ is the total area harvested of crop C in ha per year.

Below-ground residues ($BGR(C)$, kg Dm year⁻¹) is given by

$$BGR(C) = (YieldDM(C) + AG_{DM}(C)) * Ratio(C) * area(C) * FRAC_{renew}(C) \quad (64)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.6), where $YieldDM(C)$ is the harvested DM yield for crop C in kg DM per ha for which we consider farm-specific values, $Ratio(C)$ is the ratio of below-ground root biomass to above-ground shoot biomass for crop C in kg DM per ha to kg DM per ha, and $FRAC_{renew}(C)$ is the fraction of the total area under crop C that is renewed annually. For annual crops, $FRAC_{renew}(C) = 1$; for pastures renewed every 4th year, $FRAC_{renew}(C) = 0.25$.

Parts of eq. (63) and (64) can be further specified, given the following equations.

First, the above-ground residue for crop C, ($AG_{DM}(C)$; kg DM ha⁻¹) can be estimated using farm-level data on crop yields and is given by

$$AG_{DM}(C) = Yield_{DM}(C) * Ratio_{YieldAG}(C) \quad (65)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.6), where $Ratio_{YieldAG}$ is the ratio of above-ground residue in kg DM to the harvested yield ($Yield_{DM}(C)$) for crop C in kg DM (Table 29).

In some cases, it might be easier for farmer to provide the yield data on the basis of fresh matter. Depending on how the yield data is available for the DFEMS, a correction factor should be applied to convert the harvested fresh matter yield for crop C ($Yield_{FM}(C)$, kg FM ha⁻¹) to the dry matter yield, and is given by

$$Yield_{DM}(C) = Yield_{FM}(C) * FRAC_{DM}(C) \quad (66)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.7), where $Yield_{FM}(C)$ is the harvested fresh yield for crop C in kg fresh weight per ha and $FRAC_{DM}(C)$ is the DM fraction of the harvested crop C in kg DM per kg fresh weight.

The IPCC provides default values for $N_{AG}(C)$, $N_{BG}(C)$, $Ratio(C)$, $Ratio_{YieldAG}(C)$, and $FRAC_{DM}(C)$ for the major crop and forage types (Table 29). These values come with uncertainty. Therefore, it is recommended to use country-specific values, if available. As described in Section 3.1.3, the feed tables provided by LfL (2023, 2021b, 2021a) and LK Oberösterreich (2020) contain information on the DM fraction ($FRAC_{DM}(C)$) for several crop and forage types, considering different stages of harvest. The information on the nutritional content (e.g., CP) of the crop and forage types is based on the DM. When estimating direct N₂O emissions from managed soils at the farm level in Austria, the values for $FRAC_{DM}(C)$ provided by the LfL are applied.

Table 29: Default values for $N_{AG}(C)$, $N_{BG}(C)$, $Ratio(C)$, $Ratio_{YieldAG}(C)$, and $FRAC_{DM}(C)$ (adapted from IPCC, 2019; tab. 11.1A)

Crop or forage type	N content of above-ground residues $N_{AG}(C)$ (kg N (kg DM) ⁻¹)	N content of below-ground residues $N_{BG}(C)$	Ratio of above-ground residue DM to harvested yield $Ratio_{YieldAG}(C)$	Ratio of below-ground to above-ground biomass $Ratio(C)$	DM fraction of harvested crops $FRAC_{DM}(C)$
Generic value for crops not indicated below or no estimate available	0.008	0.009	1.0	0.22	0.85
Generic grains	0.006	0.009	1.3	0.22	0.88
Winter wheat	0.006	0.009	1.3	0.23	0.89
Spring wheat	0.006	0.009	1.3	0.28	0.89
Barley	0.007	0.014	1.2	0.22	0.89
Oats	0.007	0.008	1.3	0.25	0.89
Maize	0.006	0.007	1.0	0.22	0.87
Rye	0.005	0.011	1.6	-	0.88
Millet	0.007	-	1.4	-	0.90
Sorghum	0.008	0.006	1.4	-	0.89
Beans and pulses	0.008	0.008	2.1	-	0.91
Soybeans	0.008	0.008	2.1	0.19	0.91
Potatoes and tubers	0.019	0.014	0.4	0.2	0.22
Alfalfa	0.027	0.019	NA	0.40	0.90

Non-legume hay	0.015	0.012	NA	0.54	0.90
N-fixing forages	0.027	0.022	0.30	0.40	0.90
Non-N-fixing forages	0.015	0.012	0.30	0.54	0.90
Perennial grasses	0.015	0.012	0.30	0.80	0.90
Grass-clover mixtures	0.025	0.016	0.30	0.80	0.90

* Note: “-” means that no data is available.

Direct N₂O-N emissions from urine and dung inputs by grazing livestock

The **direct N₂O-N emissions from urine and dung inputs** by grazing livestock (the focus here is on cattle, swine, and poultry) to the soils (N₂O – N_{PRP}, kg N₂O-N year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_2O - N_{PRP} = F_{PRP} * EF_{N_2O,PRP} \quad (67)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.1), where F_{PRP} is the annual amount of urine and dung N deposited by grazing cattle, swine, and poultry on a pasture, range, and paddock in kg N per year, and EF_{N₂O,PRP} is the emission factor for N₂O emissions from urine and dung N deposited by grazing cattle, swine, and poultry on a pasture, range, and paddock in kg N₂O-N per kg N input.

Urine and dung deposited by grazing livestock on pasture, range and paddock to soils (F_{PRP}) requires data on the annual average amount of N excreted by each livestock category Nex(T) in kg per animal and year and on the fraction of this excreted N deposited on pasture, range, and paddock soils per livestock category (MS_{PRP}(T)). F_{PRP} (kg N year⁻¹) is given by

$$F_{PRP} = \sum_T [(AAP(T) * Nex(T)) * MS_{PRP}(T)] \quad (68)$$

(IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.5) where the prior calculated N excretion rates are applied for Nex(T) (see section 3.3.3).

Box 19: Farm-specific grazing situation for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria

In order to account for farm-specific grazing situations, we derive MS_{PRP}(T) in form of the number of grazing days per year and grazing hours per day and calculate the share of manure deposited to pasture, range, and paddock from total manure excreted by animals per livestock sub-category.

Emission factors for direct N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils

Following the tier 2 approach, as given by eq. (58), (59), and (67), two emission factors are needed for calculating the direct N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils:

- (1) the first emission factor is used for N inputs from synthetic fertilizers, organic fertilizers and crop residues (EF_{N₂O,Ninputs});
- (2) the second emission factor is used for N inputs from grazing animals (EF_{N₂O,PRP}).

Table 30 summarizes the default emission factors for direct N₂O emissions from N inputs and from urine and dung deposited by grazing cattle, swine, and poultry (IPCC, 2019). These default emission factors depend on the climate region, i.e., wet or dry climate, and the type of N input.

Table 30: Default emission factors to calculate direct N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils (Table adopted from IPCC, 2019; tab. 11.1)

Emission factor	Unit	Climate region	N input	Default value
EF _{N₂O,Ninputs}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N input) ⁻¹	wet climate	synthetic N fertilizer input	0.016
		wet climate	other N inputs	0.006
(2) EF _{N₂O,PRP}	kg N ₂ O-N (kg N input) ⁻¹	dry climates	all N inputs	0.005
		wet climates		0.006
		dry climate		0.002

Note: For Austria, we use the emission factor values assuming a wet climate.

4.2.3. Step (iii): Indirect nitrous oxide emissions from managed agricultural soils

Indirect N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils result from two processes

- (1) volatilization of N as NH₃ and NO_x as well as the deposition of their products NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ onto soils or surfaces of lakes or other water bodies; and
- (2) leaching and runoff from land in such a way that the inorganic N is not retained in the soil or vegetation and is transported to overland water flows.

In the protocol and DFEMS, the following N inputs of indirect N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils are considered:

- (1) synthetic fertilizer (F_{SN}),
- (2) organic N applied as fertilizer (F_{ON}),
- (3) urine and dung N deposited on pasture, range, and paddock by grazing animals (F_{PRP}), and
- (4) N in crop residues (F_{CR}).

Indirect nitrous oxide emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilization

The amount of indirect N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N that is volatilized from managed agricultural soils (N₂O_{G(Soils)}, kg N₂O year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_2O_{G(Soils)} = \left([F_{SN} * FRAC_{gasSoilSN}] + [(F_{ON} + F_{PRP}) * FRAC_{gasSoilM}] \right) * EF_{N_2O,ATD} * \frac{44}{28} \quad (69)$$

(adapted from IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.9), where FRAC_{gasSoilSN} is the fraction of synthetic fertilizer N that volatilizes as NH₃ and NO_x in kg N volatilized per kg of N applied, FRAC_{gasSoilM} is the fraction of applied organic N (F_{ON}) and of urine and dung N deposited by grazing livestock (F_{PRP}) that volatilizes as NH₃ and NO_x given in kg N volatilized per kg of N applied or deposited, and EF_{N₂O,ATD} is the emission factor for N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N on soils and water surfaces in kg N₂O-N per kg (NH₃-N + NO_x-N) volatilized. The N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilized from managed agricultural soils (N₂O_{G(Soils)}) are then derived by multiplying N₂O-N emissions by the conversion factor 44 * 28⁻¹.

Indirect nitrous oxide emissions from runoff and leaching

The amount of N₂O produced from leaching and runoff of N additions (N₂O_{L(Soils)}, kg N₂O year⁻¹) is given by

$$N_2O_{L(\text{Soils})} = \left((F_{SN} + F_{ON} + F_{PRP} + F_{CR}) * FRAC_{\text{leachSoil}} * EF_{N_2O,L} \right) * \frac{44}{28} \quad (70)$$

(adapted from IPCC, 2019; eq. 11.10), where $FRAC_{\text{leachSoil}}$ is the fraction of all N sources added to managed agricultural soils that is lost through leaching and runoff in kg N per kg of N additions, and $EF_{N_2O,L}$ is the emission factor for N_2O emissions from N leaching and runoff in kg N_2O -N per kg N leached and runoff. Again, N_2O emissions from leaching and runoff are obtained by multiplying the N_2O emissions by the conversion factor $44 * 28^{-1}$.

In the DFEMS, we apply a country-specific value for $FRAC_{\text{leachSoil}}$ of 15.154 % when estimating indirect N_2O emissions from leaching and runoff at the farm level. This value is based on a country-specific study that evaluated N losses through leaching and calculated the loss fraction for Austria (Anderl et al., 2024).

The IPCC provides default values for $EF_{N_2O,ATD}$, $EF_{N_2O,L}$, $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilSN}}$, and $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$ for estimating the indirect N_2O emissions from managed soils (Table 31 and Table 32). However, if more detailed data on emission, volatilization or leaching factors is available, the equations (69) and (70) for estimating $N_2O_{G(\text{Soils})}$ and $N_2O_{L(\text{Soils})}$, respectively, can be further disaggregated.

Table 31: Default emission factors for indirect nitrous oxide emissions from managed agricultural soils (IPCC, 2019, 2006; tab. 11.3)

Emission factor	Unit	Default value
$EF_{N_2O,ATD}$	kg N_2O -N per kg NH_3 -N + NO_x -N volatilized	0.01
$EF_{N_2O,L}$	kg N_2O -N per kg N leaching/ runoff	0.0075

In the DFEMS, we apply country-specific volatilization fractions, i.e., $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilSN}}$ and $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$, provided in Austria's National Inventory Report (Anderl et al., 2023b). This country-specific methodology results in country-specific values for $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilSN}}$ and $FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$ considering NH_3 -N and NO_x -N losses from

- urea and non-urea N fertilizers ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilSN}}$),
- animal manure applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$),
- dung and urine deposited by grazing animals ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$),
- sewage sludge applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$),
- biogas digestates applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$), and
- compost applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$).

The European Environment Agency (EEA; 2019) provides default emission factors that are used in the DFEMS for the non- CO_2 GHG emission accounting at the farm level. These loss fractions consider losses in form of NH_3 -N and NO_x -N from the above-mentioned N inputs and are summarized in Table 32.

Table 32: Austria specific values for the volatilization fractions (based on Anderl et al., 2023b; EEA, 2019).

Loss fractions	kg NH_3 -N (kg per N applied)	kg NO_x -N (kg NO per N applied)
Losses urea and non-urea N fertilizers ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilSN}}$)	see Table 33	0.04
Losses from animal manure applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$)	see Table 34	0.04
Losses from dung and urine deposited by grazing animals	see Table 35	0.04
Losses from sewage sludge applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$)	0.13	0.04
Losses from biogas digestates applied to agricultural soils ($FRAC_{\text{gasSoilM}}$)	0.08	0.04

Losses from compost applied to agricultural soils (FRAC _{gasSoilM})	0.08	0.04
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Moreover, the EEA provides NH₃ emission factors, disaggregated by fertilizer type and climate conditions (European Environment Agency, 2019; tab. 3.2), whereby Austria belongs to cool and temperate countries (Anderl et al., 2023b). Table 33 summarizes the emission factors for NH₃ emissions in kg NH₃ per kg N applied, which are used in the DFEMS. If information on the soil pH is available, it is possible to further account for the soil pH at the farm or even field level and to apply a specific NH₃ emission factor. However, due to a lack of information on site-specific soil characteristics, we cannot consider the soil pH in the DFEMS.

Table 33: Emission factors for NH₃ emissions by fertilizer types differentiated by climate region and soil pH in g NH₃ per kg N applied (adapted from European Environment Agency, 2019; tab. 3.2)

Fertilizer type	Cool climate		Temperate climate	
	Normal pH	High pH	Normal pH	High pH
Anhydrous ammonia (AH)	19	35	20	36
Ammonium Nitrate (AN)	15	32	16	33
Ammonium phosphate (AP)	50	91	51	94
Ammonium sulphate (AS)	90	165	92	170
Calcium Ammonium Nitrate (CAN)	8	17	8	17
NK mixtures	15	32	22	33
NPK mixtures	50	91	67	94
NP mixtures	50	91	67	94
N solutions	98	95	100	97
Other straight compounds	10	19	14	20
Urea CO(NH ₂) ₂	155	164	159	168

Note: low pH refers to values of 7.0 or below, high pH refers to values higher than 7.0;

Building on the farm-level data collected for the application examples of the DFEMS from Austria, data on the amounts of each fertilizer type applied, as well as the area it was applied to is available and can further be used for estimating the NH₃ losses from synthetic fertilizer application at the farm level.

For the NH₃-N emissions from animal manure applied to agricultural soils, we differentiate between the type of manure, the manure application method, and the manure incorporation time for each livestock category (see Table 34).

Table 34: NH₃ emission factors (expressed as a share of TAN) differentiated by the type of manure, manure application method, and incorporation time of manure for the livestock categories cattle, swine and poultry (adapted from Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021).

Type of manure*	Manure application method	Incorporation time	NH ₃ emission factors (kg NH ₃ -N (kg ⁻¹ TAN))
<i>cattle</i>			
liquid manure	broadcasting	not incorporated	0.20
liquid manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.02
liquid manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.07
liquid manure	slurry cultivator	directly	0.01
liquid manure	injection technique	directly	0.04
liquid manure	slot injection	directly	0.04
liquid manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, grassland	0.14
liquid manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, cropland	0.10
liquid manure	trailing hose	≤ 1 hour	0.01
liquid manure	trailing hose	1 to ≤ 4 hour	0.05
liquid manure	trailing shoe	not incorporated, grassland	0.08
slurry manure	broadcasting	not incorporated, grassland	0.60

slurry manure	broadcasting	not incorporated, cropland	0.50
slurry manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.10
slurry manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.26
slurry manure	slurry cultivator	directly	0.04
slurry manure	injection technique	directly	0.24
slurry manure	slot injection	directly	0.24
slurry manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, grassland	0.54
slurry manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, cropland	0.46
slurry manure	trailing hose	≤ 1 hour	0.04
slurry manure	trailing hose	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.15
slurry manure	trailing shoe	directly	0.36
solid manure	broadcasting	not incorporated	0.90
solid manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.09
solid manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.45
solid manure	broadcasting	4 to ≤ 12 hours	0.81
solid manure	broadcasting	12 to ≤ 24 hours	0.90
solid manure	broadcasting	24 to ≤ 48 hours	0.90
<i>swine</i>			
liquid manure	broadcasting	not incorporated	0.20
liquid manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.02
liquid manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.07
liquid manure	slurry cultivator	directly	0.01
liquid manure	injection technique	directly	0.04
liquid manure	slot injection	directly	0.04
liquid manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, grassland	0.14
liquid manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, cropland	0.1
liquid manure	trailing hose	≤ 1 hour	0.01
liquid manure	trailing hose	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.05
liquid manure	trailing shoe	not incorporated, grassland	0.08
slurry manure	broadcasting	not incorporated, grassland	0.30
slurry manure	broadcasting	not incorporated, cropland	0.25
slurry manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.04
slurry manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.09
slurry manure	slurry cultivator	directly	0.02
slurry manure	injection technique	directly	0.06
slurry manure	slot injection	directly	0.06
slurry manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, grassland	0.21
slurry manure	trailing hose	not incorporated, cropland	0.18
slurry manure	trailing hose	≤ 1 hour	0.02
slurry manure	trailing hose	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.06
slurry manure	trailing shoe	directly	0.12
solid manure	broadcasting	not incorporated	0.90
solid manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.09
solid manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.45
solid manure	broadcasting	4 to ≤ 12 hours	0.81
solid manure	broadcasting	12 to ≤ 24 hours	0.90
solid manure	broadcasting	24 to ≤ 48 hours	0.90
<i>poultry</i>			
solid manure	broadcasting	not incorporated	0.90

solid manure	broadcasting	≤ 1 hour	0.00
solid manure	broadcasting	1 to ≤ 4 hours	0.18
solid manure	broadcasting	4 to ≤ 12 hours	0.40
solid manure	broadcasting	12 to ≤ 24 hours	0.45

* resulting from the type of manure storage system

¹ grassland and cropland vegetation

In addition to the differentiated NH₃-N emissions from animal manure applied to agricultural soils, we apply livestock sub-category-specific NH₃ emission factors for calculating the losses from dung and urine deposited by grazing animals

Table 35: NH₃ emission factors for grazing livestock differentiated by the livestock sub-category (adapted from Arbeitsgruppe BEK, 2021)

Livestock sub-category	NH₃ emission factor (kg NH₃-N (kg⁻¹ TAN))
Other cattle >2 years (e.g., stud bulls)	0.14
Young cattle 1 – 2 years	0.14
Young cattle up to 1 year	0.14
Dairy cattle	0.14
Suckling cows	0.14
Breeding/ fattening cattle	0.14
Piglets 8 – 32 kg live weight	0.31
Breeding sows and boars	0.31
Fattening pigs	0.31
Laying hens	0.099

These disaggregated NH₃ emission factors can be applied for calculating indirect N₂O emissions at the farm level. The differentiation between manure application method and incorporation allows to capture different farm management practices.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Austria's National Inventory reports GHG emissions for the agricultural sector. The national inventory is an important tool for comparing national GHG emissions internationally and monitoring the achievement of climate targets. The data used for calculating GHG emissions is aggregated at the Austrian level and national average GHG emissions are published. However, GHG emissions at the farm level can deviate considerably from the Austrian average. Therefore, we aim to extend the national reporting by calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level, while ensuring consistency with the established IPCC approach for calculating non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agriculture (IPCC, 2006, 2019).

Non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting at the farm level requires farm-level data, in particular on livestock characteristics and performance, the feeding situation and feed rations, manure management, the application of synthetic fertilizers, as well as other N inputs to the soils. The collection of the required farm-level data comes with several challenges, both at the technical or content level, i.e., which data are to be collected and how are they collected, and the coordination and communication between various stakeholders.

From a technical or content perspective, the test run of the DFEMS has shown that much of the data additionally required for farm-level non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting is readily available and can be queried with little additional effort. This includes, for instance, details on grazing days per year and grazing hours per day, and information on feeding strategies such as phase feeding of fattening pigs. However, the test run revealed that that farm-level data on feed rations come with uncertainties, and it is challenging for farmers to provide these data.

From the farmers' perspective, selected data needs are sensitive, as they provide detailed insights into their farm management decisions. Therefore, the resulting willingness to provide this data for research

projects tends to be low. In addition, farmers already face a high level of data collection effort, e.g., for verification obligations in relation to policy payments, which also reduces their willingness to collect and provide further data. The first test run of the DFEMS showed that close cooperation between different stakeholders, i.e., farmers, scientists, and extension services or consultants, is required in order to collect detailed and comprehensive farm-level data for non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting. The cooperation has to build on trust, mutual understanding and transparency in order to ensure exhaustive (and long-term) exchange of data, information, and knowledge. In the case of the DFEMS, we make use of an established online data query tool that farmers already know and trust, which reduces the barrier for farmers to participate.

The farm-level non-CO₂ GHG emission accounting may help to identify effective and efficient mitigation measures at the farm level and inform decision-making. These farm-level calculations enable farmers to understand their specific leverage points for reducing GHG emissions related to their farm activities. Detailed non-CO₂ GHG emission calculations provide insights that support informed decision-making, about adopting technologies, alternative farm practices or strategies. Another benefit of these farm-level calculations is the monitoring aspect, i.e., farmers may assess the effectiveness of implemented measures and refine their strategies as needed.

Moreover, standardized farm-level (non-CO₂) GHG emission accounting helps to make supply chains more transparent. This is a first step towards making the costs (financial, working time) for a climate-friendly production visible. From this, farmers as well as consumers can benefit. Farmers who, e.g., sell their agricultural goods via direct marketing, can benefit from marketing advantages. (Interested) consumers can be supported in their purchasing decisions.

It has to be stressed, that the applied EF describe a linear relationship between the farming activity and the resulting non-CO₂ GHG emissions. As such, the EF fail to account, e.g., for critical drivers of N₂O emission such as regional differences in climate, soil type, and management practices. Given the current state of research and provision of EF, non-CO₂ GHG emission estimates do not accurately reflect the impact of management practices, unless they are input driven. Therefore, the calculated non-CO₂ GHG emission estimates might be flawed and need to be interpreted with caution. The present protocol does not provide any validation of the calculated non-CO₂ GHG emission results. However, validation is essential for ensuring the reliability of these results. In many cases, experimental data to verify non-CO₂ GHG emissions from agriculture is scarce or completely lacking making it difficult for any validation efforts.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Digital farm emission monitoring system (DFEMS)

Appendix 1 presents the DFEMS, an Excel-based tool developed to calculate non-CO₂ GHG emissions at the farm level. The DFEMS follows the protocol and provides a structured approach for end users, e.g., farmers or stakeholders, to calculate the non-CO₂ GHG emissions from various farming activities. The DFEMS can act as a prototype for a user-friendly platform for farm-level emission monitoring. The tool consists of two separate Excel files: the DFEMS i) for cattle farms and ii) for swine farms.

The non-CO₂ GHG emission calculation tool allows e.g., farmers, to enter their farm-level data which is the bases for the further calculations for CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, CH₄ and N₂O from manure management and N₂O from agricultural soils. Cells which require data input through the end user are highlighted.

Appendix 2: Considered feed components and the nutritional information

Appendix 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the feed components considered in this protocol, along with their respective nutritional information. This information is essential for understanding that the composition of feed rations comes with different nutrient values for the overall feed ration. The feed components tables also show different values depending on e.g., the plant growth stage at harvesting or the type of conservation, i.e., fresh grass or silage. The nutritional information includes key parameters such as metabolizable energy (ME), net energy (NE), crude protein (CP), crude ash (CA) or the dry matter content. The feed tables for swine are also used for poultry. This appendix serves as a reference point for further discussing and calculating a feed ration's composition and its nutritional values at the farm level.

Appendix 3: Pre-defined feed rations for the application examples of the DFEMS in Austria

Appendix 3 presents the pre-defined feed rations used in the application examples of the DFEMS in Austria. These pre-defined rations are stored in the query tool for the livestock categories cattle, swine and poultry. The pre-defined rations can serve as a guidance for the farmers entering their farm-specific feed ration for a specific livestock category. The farmers can change and adapt the standard rations to fit their specific farming situation.